

Title Correction (Erratum)

This note corrects English spellings/capitalization on the final page of the Persian (2017) thesis. The accurate English details are:

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Author: Hamidreza Esmailnazari

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The previously printed phrases — “Tehran Markaz,” “M.sc Thesis On Architecture,” “Kish Residential Tower with generative design/Sustainable Approach,” “Dr. vida Boraz jani,” and “Hamidreza Esmail Nazari” — are superseded by the corrected forms above. The scholarly content of the thesis is unchanged.

Author's Preface — Translation Disclosure

This document is an English translation of my Master's thesis originally submitted in Persian on 2017-06-06 (1396-03-16) to Islamic Azad University — Central Tehran Branch, Faculty of Architecture and Urbanism, Department of Architecture. The translation is faithful to the original; aside from minor editorial corrections for clarity and consistency, the research design, data, analyses, and results are unchanged.

This translation was prepared in 2025 for application purposes. It introduces no new analyses, data, or methodological changes and includes no addenda.

I confirm that I am the author of both the original 2017 thesis and this English translation; the 2017 research is original, and any commentary beyond the translated content has been avoided.

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Islamic Azad University
Central Tehran Branch (IAUCTB)
Faculty of Architecture and Urban Planning — Department of Architecture

Design of a Residential Tower

Using a Generative Design Approach

Master's Thesis in Architecture
Submitted in partial fulfilment of the requirements for

The Master's degree in Architecture

Author: Hamidreza Esmailnazari
Thesis Supervisor: Vida Borazjani, Ph.D.

Tehran, Iran — Spring 2017

Abstract

Residential complexes are a dominant response to housing demand in modern urban life, and residential towers are often an inevitable form of such complexes due to the monetary cost and environmental value of land. Soil and land are the habitat of all living beings, not only humans; with population growth relative to the occupied living surface, more land can be left for other species. At the same time, the quality of life in the built environment must be addressed alongside this predominantly quantitative perspective.

This thesis aims to design a residential tower on Kish Island using a generative design approach that incorporates the spatial characteristics of courtyard houses in order to enhance residential spatial quality. The research method is descriptive–analytical, and information has been gathered through library research, literature review, and case studies. The findings indicate that, in achieving environmental efficiency, siting and interaction with natural energies take priority; the building should be positioned to benefit from positive environmental factors. The results suggest that, through sustainable architectural design and by harnessing the region’s potential natural energies—particularly wind and humidity—a residential tower in Kish can improve spatial quality.

Keywords: *Generative design; High-rise housing; Courtyard typology; Solar shading; Sustainable architecture; Contextual architecture; Climate-responsive design; Hot–humid climate; Natural ventilation; Passive cooling; Building porosity; Indoor environmental quality; Kish Island (Iran).*

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List of Abbreviations and Acronyms:

Acronyms & Initialisms (A–Z)

BWTC: *Bahrain World Trade Center.*

DC: *Direct Current.*

ETC: *Evacuated Tube Collector (solar thermal).*

FPC: *Flat-Plate Collector (solar thermal).*

HVAC: *Heating, Ventilation, and Air-Conditioning.*

IAUCTB: *Islamic Azad University, Central Tehran Branch.*

MEP: *Mechanical, Electrical, and Plumbing (building services).*

SWH: *Solar Water Heating (system).*

WTC: *World Trade Center (as in Bahrain WTC/BWTC).*

Organizations:

IFCO: *Iranian Fuel Conservation Company (Iran).*

IPCC: *Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (United Nations).*

IISD: *International Institute for Sustainable Development (Canada).*

SUNA: *Renewable Energy Organization of Iran [former name of SATBA].*

UN: *United Nations.*

Units & Symbols:

°C: degrees Celsius.

%: percent.

CO₂: carbon dioxide.

GW: gigawatt.

kW: kilowatt.

kWh/m²: kilowatt-hour per square meter.

km/h: kilometers per hour.

m: meter.

m²: square meter.

m³: cubic meter.

m/s: meters per second.

Ø: diameter symbol.

USD: United States dollar.

1: Chapter One: Research Design

Introduction

Population growth and the depletion of resources—and, accordingly, the concentration of resources made possible by technology in cities—have increased the demand for urban residence. At the same time, the limited urban space available to accommodate this population has raised the value of land. Moreover, land is not and has never been solely a human habitat; horizontal urban expansion has reduced green spaces and the habitats of other species and has caused considerable environmental damage.

Verticalization has been one response to housing needs in recent decades. Its emergence, driven by an economic and quantitative outlook, has reduced the quality of residential spaces in towers and high-rise buildings compared with courtyard houses. In this research, an effort is made to move away from a purely economic and quantitative perspective and to bring the residential environment, to some extent, closer to that of courtyard houses.

In economic and per-capita terms, the outcome has lower efficiency than towers built purely with an economic outlook, and far greater efficiency than horizontally expanding cities; in fact, the result lies between these two approaches—between the economically driven tower that disregards the quality of residential space and the courtyard house that disregards population growth and land value.

Research Background

Extensive research has examined high-rise architecture that incorporates “green layers” and environmental performance, with notable built precedents completed before 2017. These include the Bahrain World Trade Center in Manama (integrated wind turbines), Bosco Vertical in Milan (vegetated balconies), One Central Park in Sydney (green walls and a heliostat-lit sky garden), Al Bahar Towers in Abu Dhabi (responsive mashrabiya shading), Oasia Hotel Downtown in Singapore (living façade and sky terraces), The New York Times Building in New York (ceramic-rod external sunscreen), Pearl River Tower in Guangzhou (wind-tunnel turbines and double-skin façade), Shanghai Tower in Shanghai (stacked sky-garden atria), and Commerzbank Tower in Frankfurt (nine sky gardens). Reference may also be made to books such as *Archetypal Architecture* by Dr. Mahmoud Golabchi, *Climate-Responsive Architecture (Principles of Architectural Design in Hot Regions)* by Helge Koch-Nielsen, and *Designing a Sustainable School* by Alan Ford, among others. However, with respect to bringing tower architecture closer to courtyard houses and defining the courtyard as a constituent of a residential unit within a tower, an internet search yielded no results.

1.2 Research Method and Tools

Two principal research designs—descriptive and analytical—were employed for data collection. The instruments for data gathering include observation of case examples, note-taking from library studies, databases, and computer networks (the Internet). Various methods of morphological and physical analysis of successful examples in environmentally sustainable architecture were applied through fieldwork and library research.

1.3 Problem Statement

Today, courtyard houses are far less common in cities than before the Industrial Revolution and, specifically in Iran, than before the Pahlavi period. Courtyard houses combined place of work and living under one roof. With the invention of the automobile and the emergence of streets, courtyards—the green layer of residential houses—gradually gave way to streets. Central-courtyard houses and pavilions were transformed under municipal regulations into houses with the 60/40 rule, and today even that 40 percent has been turned into ramps or parking; in effect, courtyards have disappeared. It cannot be denied that the rise in land value has contributed to the elimination of courtyards. At the same time, towers are built as economically driven structures, and every developer seeks more permits for construction. High-rise construction and

courtyards embody two opposing meanings, and this research seeks to establish an interaction between these two concepts.

1.4 Research Objectives

The objectives of the research comprise general and specific aims. Considering the subject, the project area, and the issues governing this proposal, the objectives pursued are as follows:

1.4.1 General Objectives

Organizing and equipping the shoreline as one of the principal residential and social centers for citizens and visitors. Compensating for the shortage of residential spaces, mitigating environmental pollution, observing the principles of sustainable development, and restoring spatial quality to the residential environment. Active protection of the natural environment, green spaces, and the coastal zone. Design based on climatic factors to enhance architectural sustainability.

1.4.2 Specific Objectives

Design grounded in sustainable architecture, ecological architecture, vernacular architecture, and green architecture, and the use of renewable energies and recyclable materials. Creating identity by producing a building with distinguished aesthetic and physical characteristics in the area.

Increasing relative economic efficiency.

1.5 Research Question

Can the quality of residential space found in a courtyard house be incorporated into residential towers?

1.6 Research Hypotheses

It appears that the wind-energy capacity of Kish Island can supply part of the electrical energy for a sustainable residential tower. It appears that the island's high air humidity can provide part of the water required by the residential tower.

2: Chapter Two: Theoretical Foundations

2–1 Concept of Housing and the Energy Crisis

2–2 Efficiency of Housing

Housing, or living space, must be efficient in two respects: first, in responding to and creating a comfortable environment in terms of physical conditions—namely, providing an environment with appropriate temperature, suitable pressure, reasonable humidity, and proper airflow and daylight, among others; and second, in responding to the spiritual needs of people by creating spaces suited to their way of life, culture, and social customs. If these two conditions are combined in the most complete manner, they will produce the most desirable housing; if either aspect is deficient, housing will not respond well. For example, a dwelling that is optimized in physical terms and designed with the best technology but lacks spaces appropriate to the inhabitants' way of life is by no means desirable; conversely, creating a space fully aligned with cultural conditions but lacking tolerable bio-environmental conditions is unacceptable.

The desirability of housing is also discussable both internally and externally. Internally, as noted, the dwelling should be reasonable in its physical and cultural conditions; externally, it must also be in harmony with its surrounding environment. A dwelling that is internally complete but does not sufficiently correspond to its external environment—e.g., lacking adequate cultural compatibility—will not be very desirable (Rapoport, 1388).

2–3 What Is Desirable Housing?

In the contemporary era, one of the issues facing human society is desirable housing. At present, owing to land scarcity and high housing prices, people are forced to be content with smaller floor areas for their homes, and consequently the spaces of the house must, as far as possible, be utilized and be efficient. Beyond mere usability and efficiency of space, housing must also be efficient from the viewpoint of its users—that is, it must possess conditions aligned with the needs of its users, satisfying the requirements of the individual who uses it.

The desirability of housing arises precisely from this definition and relates to the expectations that each individual or user group has of their home and strives to realize by any means possible. Creating desirable housing for users in diverse social conditions is among the responsibilities of planners, architects, and housing designers, and architects are obliged to seek the factors influencing housing desirability for people who possess their own national culture, customs, and specific expectations. Ordinary people regard the best aspect of housing desirability

to be the existence of appropriate and correct relations among family members; that is, sound social relations are the best factor in the desirability of housing (Pirnia).

Nonetheless, the factors of spatial and environmental desirability are also not without effect on housing desirability, and it is in fact the architect's duty to fulfill this role in the best possible way and to gain sufficient knowledge about the factors influencing desirability. It is useful here to consider several definitions offered by experts concerning the house.

“The house is a covering that, in adaptation to certain conditions, establishes the environmental relation between the external environment and the human biological phenomena. In the house an individual or a family must live—that is, sleep, move about, lie down, see, and think.”
(Le Corbusier)

2–4 The Necessity of Attention to Sustainable Energies

Continuation of life, the persistence of living, and global health and hygiene are concepts that have shaped humanity's efforts across various fields of knowledge (Sarabi, 1383). The issue is that our world is moving toward a new order, the changes of which are readily observable: a shift from the centrality of the West toward interaction and coexistence among diverse cultures; from logocentrism to pluralism and the parallel existence of values; a departure from anthropocentrism and a turn toward ecological issues and the coexistence of species—or, more precisely, a shift from the machine age to the information society. Accordingly, it seems that a great intellectual revolution is underway worldwide, one that will have significant effects on human ways of life and thought. One such effect is the increased attention to sustainable architecture (Ali-Nejad, 1383).

In fact, just as the abandonment of vernacular architecture was accompanied by neglect of its fundamental principles and methods, the adoption of modern architecture was limited to appropriating its shell and appearance (Aminzadeh, 1383). With the emergence of modern architecture and the increasing use of mechanical systems, the importance of climate in architecture was overlooked. However, in view of the depletion of finite oil reserves, urban pollution, and the irreparable environmental damage caused by fossil fuels, attention to climate and climatic design once again came to the fore from the mid-1350s [1970s] (Ghobadian, 1382).

Gandhi says: *“The earth has enough bounty to satisfy every man's need, but not every man's greed.”* With the emergence of serious environmental issues—such as global warming, the destruction of natural resources, and environmental pollution—authorities have sought serious solutions to address these problems. Stating this does not imply that no attention has previously

been paid to such dilemmas. For more than thirty years, owing to severe environmental crises, the relationship between human and nature has been included among specialized discussions, such that topics like sustainable development, the use of natural energies, and the turn toward environmental issues have even, at times, been placed at the top of many governments' agendas.

2–5 Energy Crisis

Since the Industrial Revolution—approximately two hundred and fifty years ago—human reliance on energy, especially fossil energy, has increased exponentially (Battle McCarthy Consulting Engineers, 2006). Humanity has an insatiable appetite for energy. Global energy demand has roughly tripled since 1950, such that today the energy consumed is equivalent to 10,000 million tons of oil per year. According to the World Energy Organization, energy consumption will increase by about 50 percent by 2020. Most of our required energy is supplied by fossil fuels—coal, gas, and especially oil, which has become the most vital energy source on the planet (Walisiewicz, 2005). It should be noted that in Iran, as in other countries, environmental problems persist—particularly urban pollution and the decline of oil reserves—which has led to energy conservation and the use of clean, renewable energies becoming an important and actively pursued agenda (Battle McCarthy Consulting Engineers, 2006).

2–6 Environmental Pollution

In the coming decades, economic and political forces will resist reductions in the consumption of fossil fuels, yet a more serious concern will drive the greatest change in our consumption patterns—damage to the environment. Although the use of fuel for industrial production, transportation, and the provision of environmental comfort for humans has been vital and necessary, the consumption of fossil energy has polluted and degraded the environment, endangering ecosystems and the continuation of life on Earth. In view of this, from the second half of the past century, and especially since the 1970s, climate and environmental protection have received constant attention, and environmentalist groups have formed across the globe. These groups have primarily called for the preservation and restoration of the environment, the use of technologies compatible with the natural milieu, the recycling of industrial waste, and the use of clean energies such as solar, wind, and water (Battle McCarthy Consulting Engineers, 2006).

The burning of coal in power plants produces excess gases that combine with atmospheric moisture to form clouds containing sulfuric and nitric acids. Acid clouds can travel long distances from the pollution source before precipitating as rain. This acid rain immediately damages tree leaves and, in freshwater lakes, leads to fish die-offs. We are in the formative period

of a global environmental crisis—a crisis that governments and industry must address. In the short term, technical and specialized solutions will buy us time. The prudent use of nuclear energy, the conversion of energy types, and strict monitoring of pollutant emissions will extend the useful life of current fossil-fuel resources (Marek Walisiewicz, 2005).

2–7 The Genesis of Sustainability

With the end of the Middle Ages, the Renaissance—an era of rebirth and renewed life—emerged in the fourteenth century with a fresh outlook on the universe. Anthropocentrism, realism, and rationalism were among its principal approaches, and during this period the domains of science and religion became separated. Empirical orientations in this era led to the discovery of new phenomena, the unveiling of nature’s secrets, and the equipping of humans with advanced tools; thus, the foundations of new technology were also formed. Owing to the importance of “knowledge,” new empirical sciences came into being, and conditions arose for the rapid development of science and, consequently, technology. In this way, with the chain of scientific discoveries in the seventeenth and eighteenth centuries, the Industrial Revolution began. The scientific–industrial revolution was one of the main factors that profoundly influenced the advancement of modernist thought in the West. A new world emerged in which life was dictated by machines rather than nature and humanity. Thus, humankind entered the modern era. Modern civilization was oriented toward welfare, and nature had neither place nor value within it, such that humans adopted a servile, exploitative view of nature. The new world was based on empirical science, philosophy grounded in science, and possession of technology. Western civilization, which in the Middle Ages had been subdued, after the Renaissance assumed a position in which it could make decisive choices and attain full independence. In this period, the control of disease and the development of hygiene led to population growth, and rising population and the expansion of trade brought about rapid urbanization and the growth of cities (Rahmani, 2007). Yet after a quarter century of rapid economic growth and two decades of development, the entire planet realized that it had fallen prey to a highly dangerous development crisis that could by no means be regarded as temporary or passing (*ibid.*).

It appears that the urban structure after the Industrial Revolution, by following revivalist development patterns and the unwise adoption of unsustainable urban models, has paid no heed to local conditions and characteristics, generating not only instability within cities but also instability in surrounding regions. Today, the term “sustainability” is widely used to describe a world in which natural systems can continue life together far into the future (Bahraini, 2001). “Sustainable” means stable and durable—something that remains constant and enduring. The

sustainability of phenomena arises from the durability of the pattern, method, or system of phenomena over long periods of time. In this state, the essence of the phenomenon with all its material and immaterial attributes does not itself remain unchanged; rather, in each period it is repeated according to a single or stable pattern and thereby continues. In this repetition and reiteration, it corrects itself and, in each period, seeks greater harmony with its surrounding conditions (Pakzad, 2002). The term “sustainability” is applied to self-sustaining and self-recovering ecosystems that possess certain thresholds of tolerance—a system that ultimately leads to the endurance of the ecosystem (Miller, 1987). The term does not express the minimization of resource costs for prolonging life; rather, it states the fact that no human-made environment can live and persist without the participation of the natural environment and its ecological system (Azerbaijani; Mofidi, 2004).

Alongside the critique of modernity as a thought that engenders development, a turn toward tradition as an alternative for discerning the secrets of sustainability—embracing a holistic viewpoint in opposition to analytical thinking; accepting the governance of nature over human destiny instead of the domination of humans over nature; viewing time as continuous and unbroken rather than limited to the lifespan of an individual or a generation; and attending to scale and the creation of humanly fitting conditions instead of abstract and mechanistic organization—was once again drawn from tradition and re-examined. Thus, it may be said that the theory of sustainability and matters that are not confined to a single generation or era were derived from traditional thought. This understanding did not remain at the level of theory; to deepen these insights, traditional exemplars were also scrutinized (Ahmadi, 2007). True sustainability is associated with building design that achieves maximum energy efficiency while using renewable materials (Lashgari, 2003). In fact, “sustainable” and “sustainability” became two key terms in defining certain principles after the Rio Declaration. Sustainability is responsive to activities and developments that are able to preserve the global environment and its nonrenewable resources for the present and the future.

There are various ideas concerning sustainability, some of which are as follows:

- The next generation is the most important (Confucius).
- Treat the earth well; it is not given to you by your parents; it is loaned to you by your children (Kenyan proverb).
- Sustainability means living according to inclination rather than law (students of economics).

- Sustainability is an essential condition to prevent the severance of the bond between ecology, economy, and social security. Sustainable development requires that economic advances and social living conditions be in harmony with the natural principles of life.
- A sustainable system provides services without depleting resources and consumes all resources in an appropriate manner, both in environmental perception and in economic terms.

2–8 History of Sustainability

The discussion of sustainability was introduced by John Elkington and Julia Hailes in 1987, a few months before the publication of the Brundtland Commission Report on sustainable development.

During the following two decades, the subject of sustainability was advanced by the leadership of several companies worldwide, and more than forty definitions of it appeared in journals such as *The Triple Bottom Line* and *The Green Consumer*.

The roots of the environmental conservation movement and sustainable architecture go back to the nineteenth century. John Ruskin, William Morris, and Richard Lethaby are regarded as pioneers of sustainable architecture. Ruskin, in *The Seven Lamps of Architecture*, argued that the harmonic order found in nature could serve as a model for growth and progress. Morris advocated a return to suburban green spaces, self-sufficiency, and the revival of local crafts. Lethaby, in one of his influential manifestos, urged architects to appreciate the order and beauty of nature. All of these pioneers emphasized “nature,” and today the term that best succeeds this concept is “sustainable architecture.”

Years later, architects such as Frank Lloyd Wright, Peter Eisenman, and others continued and expanded upon these pioneers’ ideas. The flourishing of the sustainable architecture movement was not extinguished by the materialist trends of modernism. By the late twentieth century, an intriguing synthesis of building design—referred to as “cold ecology,” combining precise engineering, computer applications, and ecology—emerged (Soflaei, 2006).

Key events from the late modernist period leading to the emergence of sustainable development between 1962 and 2002 may be summarized as follows:

- 1962: The concept of “sustainable development” introduced for the first time in the field of agriculture.
- 1968: The “Biosphere Conference” held by the United Nations with multiple governments on environmental degradation.

- 1970: The UN declared June 5 as “World Environment Day.”
- 1971: The Greenpeace organization was founded in Canada to protect the environment.
- 1972: The United Nations Conference on the Human Environment held in Stockholm, Sweden, where the issue of acid rain was discussed; environmental protection agencies established in many countries.
- 1973: The Arab oil embargo following the Arab–Israeli war severely impacted developed Western nations.
- 1974: Hazards of CFC gases and ozone layer depletion became widely recognized.
- 1976: The first UN Habitat Conference on Human Settlements held (now convened every two years).
- 1977: UN Conference on Desertification highlighted the risk of expanding deserts (World Day to Combat Desertification: June 17).
- 1982: Publication of a major UN report on the global environment.
- 1985: Establishment of a division of the World Meteorological Organization (WMO); a conference in Australia on climate change.
- 1987: Presentation of the Brundtland Report “Our Common Future” in Sweden by Gro Harlem Brundtland, introducing the term sustainable development; a concurrent Canadian conference on ozone depletion and CFC use.
- 1988: The first meeting of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC).
- 1990: Establishment of the International Institute for Sustainable Development (IISD) in Canada.
- 1992: UN Earth Summit in Rio de Janeiro, Brazil; formal definition of “sustainable development” and adoption of Agenda 21, a comprehensive global action plan. The United States, Israel, and Australia declined to sign.
- 1997: UN conference in Zimbabwe reviewing five years of progress; Kyoto Protocol in Japan defined greenhouse gas emission limits per country, highlighting that the U.S. produced 30% of global pollution; the U.S. did not ratify the protocol.
- 2000: Review of global environmental conditions by world leaders at Malmö, Sweden.
- 2002: The World Summit on Sustainable Development in Johannesburg, South Africa, reviewing progress from 1992–2002, concluded with the warning: “The world is on a downward path and vigilance is required” (Rahmani, 2007).

2-9 Sustainable Structure

After the Rio Summit, the concept of sustainable development was commonly misinterpreted in Iran as being exclusively environmental in focus. However, the concept of development and its main elements on the one hand, and sustainable development on the other, point to the necessity of coordination and balance among the three domains of environment, economy, and society. Achieving sustainable development is not possible without the active and effective participation of society, which itself depends on the establishment, strengthening, and empowerment of civic institutions.

The structure of sustainability comprises several dimensions (Ahmadi, 2003):

- Environmental Sustainability
- Social Sustainability
- Economic Sustainability

2-9-1 Environmental Sustainability

The idea of environmental sustainability is based on the principle of leaving the earth in a proper state for future generations. According to one definition, human activities are environmentally sustainable only if:

- Activities do not lead to the depletion of natural resources or the destruction of the natural environment.
- Resource consumption is minimized.
- Materials used are either fully recyclable or derived from renewable sources, so that their use does not damage the environment or diminish resources.
- The water cycle is fully restored.
- Energy is preserved, renewable, and non-polluting (e.g., solar thermal, electricity, wind power, biomass, etc.).
- Key indicators in environmental sustainability objectives include:
- Minimizing fossil fuel consumption in material production, transport, construction, and building use.
- Maximizing the use of recyclable and renewable materials.
- Avoiding all chemicals that damage the ozone layer during production or use.
- Replacing materials that degrade and cause environmental pollution.
- Designing for maximum daylight use, even in locations with limited access.

- Utilizing natural ventilation systems within an overall environmental control strategy to reduce energy use and enhance comfort.
- Maximizing passive solar techniques for heating and cooling throughout the year.
- Ensuring building controls are simple and not overly complex.
- Identifying opportunities within the site for generating electrical energy.
- Exploring the potential for harnessing geothermal movements.
- Minimizing water use, ensuring wastewater treatment, and reusing water.
- Reducing rainwater loss through permeable landscaping and appropriate water collection systems.
- Creating pleasant outdoor environments through shading, moderating summer sunlight, and enhancing humidity when necessary.
- Ensuring that all of the above measures are achieved at the highest professional and technical standards, combined with outstanding aesthetic quality (Ahmadi, 2003).
- The main aspects of environmental sustainability include:
 - Waste reduction and decreased discharge into the environment.
 - Reduced harm to human health.
 - Use of renewable raw materials.

2–9–2 Social Sustainability

Social sustainability addresses the cultural characteristics of societies and the development of solutions that align with the social, cultural, and intellectual conditions of a community.

Recent studies indicate that economic development is not possible without socio-cultural development, which itself is shaped by complex socio-economic factors. These behaviors gradually become social norms, making them difficult to change in the long term (Ahmadi, 2003).

Some components of social sustainability include (Nasiri, 2000):

- Human beings: In sustainable development, humans are the center of development, entitled to health, a productive life, and harmony with nature. This is reflected in Principle One of the Rio Declaration.
- Children and youth: Educating them on environmental risks and instilling values, concepts, and strategies is the most important factor in the continuity and deepening of sustainable development.
- Women: Women deserve equal status and recognition for their natural and social responsibilities.

- Environment: Effective management and scientific approaches in resource use must ensure not only the present but also the future.
- Culture: Development must not eliminate cultural diversity or the varied experiences of nations.
- Education: Human capital is the most important resource of a country in a sustainable future. Education bridges the past, present, and future, and thus a fundamental rethinking of educational systems is required as the first step.
- Science: In the debate on sustainable development, science has a dual importance—both for its dynamism and for its attention to fundamentals. New challenges require new tools.
- Ethics: The integration of ethics and spirituality in sustainable development studies became an undeniable necessity in the final years of the twentieth century.
- Security: In the modern era, sustainable development has become a strategy for global security, with global and human security at its core.
- Participation: Development without democracy is neither reasonable nor possible.
- Aspects of social sustainability include:
 - Health and safety of workers.
 - Improving the quality of life in local communities.
 - Benefits for marginalized groups, such as the disabled.

2–9–3 Economic Sustainability

Economic sustainability entails organizing financial resources so that benefits reach the general public, enabling all social groups to benefit. This ensures a fair distribution of income and wealth and prevents the widening of class divides.

Economic dimensions of sustainability include:

- Creating new markets and opportunities to increase sales.
- Reducing costs through improved efficiency and decreased consumption of energy and raw materials.
- Generating additional added value.

The net benefit of economic development is contingent upon preserving the services and quality of natural resources. Present decisions must not jeopardize future standards of living. This requires that economic systems be managed in a way that, even if society lives beyond its allocated resources, financial foundations are preserved and enhanced.

In modern societies, the economic system is based on maximum consumption. However, in a sustainable perspective, optimal production replaces overproduction, optimal consumption replaces overconsumption, and quality takes precedence over quantity. Factories shift competition from quantity to quality, and in advertising, durability and performance replace novelty and disposability. In this sustainable system, nothing in nature is redundant or wasteful; the life cycle continues unbroken, without any element being excluded from it (Rahmani, 2007).

2-10 Development

The concept of development has undergone highly variable and extensive definitions in recent decades. In the years immediately following World War II, the term was used almost exclusively to mean economic growth. Theorists such as Walt W. Rostow described development as a multi-stage process passing through phases such as traditional society, transitional stage, take-off, and maturity, ultimately reaching the highest stage of economic growth, namely “mass consumption.”

This definition of development was also accepted by the United Nations, which declared the 1960s the First Development Decade for developing countries. However, it soon became clear that social conditions in the developing world had not improved, revealing that equating development with “economic growth alone” was mistaken. Consequently, characteristics such as poverty reduction and social equity were incorporated into the concept of development, guiding the Second Development Decade beginning in the 1970s.

2-10-1 Key Concepts of Development

The term development was introduced to avoid the ambiguity of the word growth. Unlike “growth,” which refers primarily to the physical and quantitative expansion of the economic system, “development” carries a qualitative dimension concerned with advancement and progress encompassing cultural, social, and economic aspects (Golkar, 2000).

If development is understood as a transition from one stage to another, it rests on three core ideas:

- **Evolution** — the process of change over a long period of time.
- **Progress** — a dynamic, forward-moving trajectory of change through time.
- **Human-centeredness** — placing people at the core, treating economic resources not as an end but as a means, supporting the opportunities of future generations alongside the

present, while respecting the ecological systems upon which all life depends (Soflaei, 2006).

Those who use the term “development,” particularly outside the Arab world, have already implicitly adopted the foundations of modern Western thought. To speak of “development” entails acknowledging the concept of “underdevelopment,” and thus accepting the idea that programs modeled on “developed countries” must be implemented. Therefore, it is emphasized that:

1. The theoretical underpinnings of imported ideas must first be critically examined.
2. Efforts must be made to establish a national framework for engaging with new theories.
3. Criteria derived from an indigenous worldview, including Islamic principles and national culture, should guide the evaluation of imported plans and policies (Taghizadeh, 2000).

2-10-2 The Concept of Sustainable Development

Sustainable development is not limited to environmental protection alone. Rather, it represents a new conception of economic growth that ensures well-being and opportunities for all people, preventing the exploitation of the world’s natural resources by a few for personal gain. Sustainable development is a process in which economic, financial, trade, energy, agricultural, and industrial policies are designed to ensure stability across economic, social, and ecological dimensions. This includes adequate investment in education, health, population management, and energy, without creating a social debt for future generations.

The concept, which emerged strongly at the close of the 20th century, reflects a synthesis of critical reflection on modernity and an ecological reorientation. While modernity pursued ideals of prosperity, freedom, and equality, it often neglected the destructive consequences for nature and humanity. Sustainable development thus arose as a corrective, emphasizing a balance between human progress and environmental stewardship (Ahmadi, 2003).

Although the idea of sustainable development is not new, its global prominence today stems from the fact that pre-industrial societies tended to develop in ways more closely attuned to the natural environment. Principles derived from the worldview of each civilization must guide all dimensions of activity, both material and spiritual. In contemporary usage, however, sustainable development often emphasizes the physical and material aspects of the environment, with the

protection of ecological resources and sustainable economic growth as the main objectives (Naghizadeh, 2000).

The widely cited definition of sustainable development, formulated by the World Commission on Environment and Development (WCED, 1987), states:

“Sustainable development is development that meets the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs.”

2-10-3 Theories of Sustainable Development

Numerous additional definitions of sustainable development have been proposed, some broad and general, others concise. The essential aim is to stabilize the pace of change in human living standards through a system that allows such improvements to be maintained indefinitely.

Key principles emphasized include:

1. **Future generations** — responsibility to provide them with natural resources and cultural-scientific capital.
2. **Environment** — responsibility for effective protection and management of land, water, and biodiversity.
3. **Equity** — responsibility for ensuring equal access to resources locally and globally.
4. **Public participation** — ensuring access to information and democratic processes for environmental decision-making (Soflaei, 2006).

2-10-4 Strategies for Sustainable Development

To realize sustainable development, numerous strategies have been proposed. The foremost principle concerns the use of vital human resources—energy, water, and materials—such that they remain available for future generations. This requires:

- Careful consumption of resources.
- Ensuring that what remains re-enters natural cycles through recycling, with minimal pollution.

The sustainability approach, characterized by holistic and integrative thinking, addresses three fundamental dimensions—**economy, society and culture, and environment**—not in isolation but in their interconnections. Decisions are most valid when they approach the intersection of these three domains (Ahmadi, 2003).

2–11 Sustainable City

Low urban density is not compatible with the principles of a sustainable city. The idea of the compact city—shorter travel distances, reduced consumption and waste, and shared infrastructure—aligns with the concept of urban sustainability. In addition to the common term “sustainability,” another term used in urban planning with the same meaning is “vitality and survival,” referred to by Lynch in 1981. The two terms are closely related, as both seek to promote a type of urbanism that can enhance citizens’ well-being over the long term. A city is sustainable when it strives for greater efficiency in resource use, environmental quality, social justice, and public vitality, while reducing the consumption of nonrenewable resources, the production of hazardous waste, and inequality. The principal urban-level issues are: lower energy consumption, greater homogeneity, and more equitable and efficient use of facilities (Bahraini, 2001).

The theoretical foundations of sustainability in the city may be summarized as follows (Rahmani, 2007):

- Reducing air pollution.
- Developing systems with minimal pollution.
- Emphasizing energy conservation both during city construction and during operation (at present, roughly 60–70 percent of global energy consumption occurs in cities).
- Using renewable and non-fossil energies in cities.
- Conserving natural resources.
- Reducing the volume of urban waste.
- Increasing recycling, especially of materials.
- Urban deconcentration and reduction of sprawl.
- Increasing medium densities in suburban areas and small cities.
- Reducing travel distances.
- Achieving a balanced social structure and social justice.
- Creating local employment.
- Developing small cities to reduce reliance on large cities.
- Public transportation and traffic reduction.

- Managing non-recyclable waste.
- Distributing resources and securing a sustainable local food supply.

2–11–1 Architecture and Its Relationship to the Subfields of Sustainability

Architecture is not a pure art; hence it is classed among the “applied arts.” Yet it shares a quality with all the arts: it must be for the people and with the people. As Arnold Hauser notes, “*Ruskin was also the first in England to emphasize that art is a matter pertaining to the public.*” Nevertheless, the difference between architecture and art in the general sense—especially where the relationship of architecture and the public is at issue—must be recognized. Architecture has two principal dimensions: functional and aesthetic (Mozayani, 2002).

Architecture arises from human thought and is formed through the synthesis of history, beliefs, customs, and climate; it belongs more to culture than to civilization. Architecture does not merely reflect its time; it must also reveal the crises of each era and expose the enigma of an autonomous system of thought. To think architecturally is not merely to grapple with superficial issues or to solve functional problems. Architects must learn always to pose fundamental questions so that their own architectural imagination may rise freely and enable them to understand people, life, history, beliefs, customs, and climate. We must create architectural space in such a way that human beings can experience wonder, discovery, excitement, mental stimulation, tranquility, and, fundamentally, the enjoyment of life—just as is the case with literature and music (Kashani, 1997).

2–11–1–2 Sustainable Architecture

Sustainable architecture comprises a combination of values: aesthetics, environment, society, politics, and ethics. It is the practice of applying these values and bodies of knowledge and integrating them around a central concern—harmony with the environment. Successful architecture, logically, addresses durability, longevity, sustainability, appropriate materials, and sense of place, and seeks to balance environmental and economic requirements. In this global movement, architects, in step with other scholars, have sought new strategies to provide a desirable human life. Life, work, leisure, rest, and all other activities occur in spaces designed by architects; because a building’s weaknesses and strengths have direct effects on the global ecosystem, architects bear a highly sensitive responsibility in this regard. Applying the concepts of sustainability in architecture has opened a discourse called sustainable architecture, ecological architecture, green architecture, and environmental architecture—all with a shared meaning, indicating architecture compatible with the environment (Soflaei, 2006).

Sustainable design is a mode of intervention in the environment that seeks to devise solutions which, through a holistic and integrated perspective, achieve a balance among environmental, social, and economic goals so as to provide a higher quality of life for the present generation and an appropriate legacy for future generations (Ahmadi, 2003). Because sustainability's primary concern is attention to environmental conditions, environmentally sustainable design approaches the design product in a way that maximizes the advantages inherent in the site and environmental conditions while minimizing the adverse conditions resulting from construction. From the design stage and siting, buildings must respond properly to context and conditions while minimizing confrontation with nature.

Sustainable architecture is a comprehensive matter that, like previous design tendencies, leads to architectural styles; although its primary concern is the environment, it draws upon all prior trends that emphasized reduced use of materials and energy—such as high-tech architecture, green architecture, intelligent architecture, environmental design, behavior-oriented architecture, and economy-driven architecture—while distinguishing itself from earlier architectures that pursued mere function or pure form. Sustainable design may be described as a type of architecture that makes maximum use of environmental potentials for user comfort and employs intelligent tools and strategies to do so. This type of architecture, rather than merely placing a building on a site (as has often been done), becomes, as far as possible and appropriate to the scale and program, unified with the site and an inseparable part of it.

At the urban scale, sustainable architecture likewise becomes, according to scale and function, an inseparable part of broader, interconnected urban systems. In this architecture, building materials and components are recyclable, and spaces can be repeatedly reorganized; thus, through flexibility in responding to changing user demands, demolition is avoided (Ahmadi, 2003).

Sustainability is chiefly attainable through the following:

- Intelligent design: shaping the building and controlling adverse environmental factors, converting them into beneficial, efficient agents.
- Use of intelligent building fabric: creating a responsive façade that maximizes daylight, optimizes natural air movement, and regulates solar exchange.
- Optimal use of materials: considering the embodied environmental costs of building materials, energy issues, extending building life, drawing on technologies from other industries, and employing advanced, non-polluting production tools.

- Intellectual and scientific capital: analyzing building behavior, employing CFD prototyping, and close collaboration with experts and consultants leading to intelligent use of thermal mass, buffer zones, thermal flywheels, efficient ventilators, and similar strategies (Lashgari, 2003).

2–11–2 Definitions of Sustainable Architecture

Richard Rogers's view of sustainable design:

A sustainable design is one that seeks to meet present needs without destroying the natural resource reserves that belong to future generations. Such a design must attend to the principles of social and economic sustainability and focus primarily on energy use and its effects on the environments of buildings and cities (Lashgari, 2003).

2–11–2–1 Objectives of Sustainable Architecture

Battle McCarthy, regarding the threefold goals in sustainable architecture (environmental, social, economic), notes the following (Ahmadi, 2003):

Environmental objectives: creating superior environmental quality; reusability; eliminating waste and residues; using low-transform materials; material recycling; recycling water from wastewater; eliminating pollutant emissions.

Economic objectives: generating higher value; reducing operating costs; reducing energy consumption; providing flawless, easily producible solutions; forward-looking solutions.

Social objectives: safety; adaptability; delivering quality; eliminating energy poverty; acoustic insulation; flexible programs; healthy living; home care; lifelong education; home delivery; adaptability.

In fact, the objectives of environmentally sustainable design may be summarized as follows (ibid.):

1. Maximizing human comfort through: daylight capture; pleasant views; appropriate air quality; suitable acoustic insulation; proper temperature control; desired humidity control; effective quality maintenance; necessary safety provisions; appropriate manual controls.
2. Efficient planning for: appropriate user flow and movement; achievable security; ease of adaptation and change; responsiveness to user needs; integration of structure and services.

3. Designing for change, through: simple, modular design that can adapt to growth and increased needs; facilitating plan and functional changes within the building.
4. Minimizing operating energy costs by: maximizing use of “free” energies such as daylight, solar heat, and wind; controlling temperature fluctuations through appropriate thermal insulation; effective environmental control methods; efficient building systems; and the use of plants.
5. Maximizing usable space by: reducing internal garden areas; minimizing air-duct space; maximizing integration of structural and service elements; eliminating the need for suspended ceilings.
6. Minimizing construction costs by: reducing service spaces and plant rooms; reducing complexity in spaces and service elements; coordinating dimensions of structure and services; using efficient structural systems.
7. Protecting and enhancing natural values by: integrating with wildlife and fauna; attending to green and blue infrastructures; collecting rainwater and recycling fresh water; effective wastewater recycling and reuse.

2–11–3 Sustainable Buildings

According to one project, the defining characteristic of sustainable buildings is that they impose the least harmful effects on the built and natural environment—at the scale of the building itself, neighboring buildings, wider areas, and the global condition. Sustainable buildings may be understood as construction methods aimed at creating proper conditions—in economic, social, and environmental performance—across a broad spectrum. Accordingly, the rational use of natural resources and appropriate management of building capital help conserve scarce resources, reduce fuel consumption (conserve energy), and improve environmental quality. Sustainable buildings consider the full life cycle of the building, make use of environmental conditions, address performance requirements, and assess future values.

In the past, in many countries’ attention focused largely on the size of buildings, and the discussion of quality played only a minor role, even though housing supply had saturated markets quantitatively. Demand to assess buildings in terms of quality has therefore grown, and policies that support the adoption of sustainable construction methods must expand. Recognizing current market conditions, both environmental innovation within the construction sector and consumer demand are key drivers. Governments can create significant incentives for sustainable construction by encouraging such developments.

2–11–4 Definitions of Sustainable Buildings

- The following definitions may be offered for sustainable buildings (Soflaei, 2006):
- Buildings that have the least adverse impacts on the built and natural environment over their life cycle and at local, regional, and global scales.
- Sustainable building may be a construction practice and an effort to achieve proper quality (including the roles of economy, society, and environment) across a wide field.
- The rational consumption and proper management of natural resources can conserve scarce resources, reduce energy use, and enhance environmental quality.
- A sustainable building takes into account the complete life cycle of the building, environmental quality, functional quality, and future values.

2–11–5 Objectives of Sustainable Construction

Objectives of sustainable construction include (Soflaei, 2006):

- Resource efficiency.
- Energy efficiency (including the reduction of greenhouse gas emissions).
- Pollution prevention (including indoor air quality and noise reduction).
- Harmony with the environment (including environmental assessment).
- Integrated and systematic approaches (including environmental management systems).

2–11–5–1 Selected Principles for Building Sustainability

Based on evidence from the Building Research Establishment and assessment methods, the following principles are proposed:

- Demolition and reconstruction should occur only when buildings are no longer reusable in economic or functional terms (repair and extend existing buildings).
- Transport during demolition, repair, and construction should be minimized and strictly controlled during execution to reduce noise, dust, vibration, pollution, and waste.
- All aspects of the site—historical studies, microclimatic aims, prevailing winds and climate type, solar orientation, provision for public transport, and the form of surrounding buildings—must be considered.
- Design the building to minimize the owner’s operating costs and its environmental footprint through maintainable strategies and the integration of techniques and technologies that conserve energy and water and reduce emissions to land, water, and air.

- Wherever possible, employ vernacular construction techniques, draw inspiration from local forms, and use locally appropriate materials and design.
- Prioritize building performance and occupant comfort through client–designer collaboration, addressing safety, flexibility and adaptability for future needs, upgradability, and facilitation of communication among users.
- Construct with appropriate quality and durability. Longevity depends on form; end-of-life methods and deconstruction planning are as important as using reusable materials.

The south-facing elevation of a building enables full use of winter sun for light and heat. Balconies and overhangs above windows prevent excessive solar gain in interior spaces during summer (Sultan-Zadeh, 2003). Windows are made double-glazed to minimize heat transfer and are carefully designed and constructed to resist air infiltration. A window above the stair and on the roof both supplies light to the central space and serves for summer ventilation. External walls and the roof are thick and multi-layer insulated, so heat exchange between inside and outside is very limited; the floor is also fully insulated, as visible in section. Part of the internal heat demand is supplied by occupants, lighting, and appliances; only a small portion during cold periods is provided by heaters. For part of the domestic hot water, roof-mounted solar collectors of about five square meters are used, supplying roughly half the required hot water.

Summer ventilation is provided mainly by opening windows.

- Avoid using nonrenewable resources and materials that cannot re-enter life cycles, especially in short-lived structures (Soflaei, 2006).

2–12 Sustainable Structure

A sustainable structure is defined as the responsible creation and management of a healthy built environment founded on resource efficiency and ecological principles. The goal of sustainable building design is the efficient use of resources and environmental energy, including the following principles:

- Minimizing consumption of nonrenewable resources.
- Enhancing and expanding the natural environment.
- Eliminating or minimizing the use of toxic compounds.

A sustainable structure is a subset of sustainable design, itself a subset of sustainable development. It is a structure that effectively integrates low-energy design with materials that have

minimal environmental impacts in production and use and that support ecological diversity (Soflaei, 2006).

2-12-1 Requirements of a Sustainable Structure

These definitions imply the following requirements:

- Minimizing the consumption of nonrenewable resources.
- Recovering and reusing building materials or waste materials.
- Strengthening and preparing the natural environment in product selection.
- Identifying and pursuing quality in construction and composition.
- Eliminating or reducing the use of toxic substances.
- Networking to create structures and beneficial interdependencies.
- Learning from experience and building an environmental knowledge base.
- Alerting others to the risks inherent in the building life cycle.
- Minimizing waste and preventing on-site pollution.
- Using the outputs of one process as inputs to other processes (e.g., the embodied energy of materials).

It is important that these and related definitions and core rules be observed in sustainable design. The following relationships are crucial and appropriate to sustainable structure (author) (Fig. 2-1):

- Human beings and the natural environment.
- Energy production and efficiency.
- Tradition and continuity.

Figure 2-1

Accordingly, the constituent details of a sustainable structure may be examined below (author) (Fig. 2-2).

Figure 2-2

However, there is also a need to balance environmental, social, and technological factors that make it possible to identify a sustainable structure.

2–13 Flexibility in Sustainability

“Sustainable” means stable and enduring—something that remains constant and persistent. The sustainability of phenomena arises from the durability of their patterns, methods, or systems over long periods. In this state, the essence of the phenomenon with all its material and immaterial attributes does not itself remain unchanged; rather, in each era it is repeated according to a single or stable pattern and thereby continues. Through this repetition, it corrects itself and, in each period, strives for greater harmony with its surroundings (Pakzad, 2002).

2–14 Ecological Design

Van der Ryn defines the following principles in ecological design (Aminzadeh, 2003):

- Solutions arise from the place itself.
- Ecological accounting, and information that reflects ecological costs and benefits, is essential for design decisions.
- Natural forms and processes should be allowed to guide the design.
- Everyone is a designer; therefore, all knowledge contributed to the process should be respected.

Architectural design based on ecological criteria and principles is a dimension of sustainable architecture. These and other definitions of ecological design emphasize *environmental identity*.

According to Rapoport, environmental identity results from the interaction of three factors: human beings, environment, and culture. The newer approach to green architecture—which orients building design toward optimal energy use and the application of recycled materials—together with attention to landform patterns and local characteristics (history, culture, and nature), constitutes the core of ecological applications in architectural design developed over the last two decades. On this basis, ecological design emphasizes:

- designing to confer meaning on place;
- deriving solutions to design problems from the environment;
- designing in response to environmental conditions and people;
- incorporating public input in design;
- designing with nature;
- evaluating design impacts on the environment.

Van der Ryn summarizes ecological-design principles as: solutions arising from place; ecological accounting to inform decisions; allowing natural forms and processes to guide design; and recognizing that everyone is a designer (Aminzadeh, 2003).

2–14–1 Ecology (Ecosystem Science)

Ecology is the science that investigates how organisms live within the systems that sustain their life. The term derives from the Greek *oikos* (dwelling, habitat) and *logos* (study or knowledge), and literally means the study of living organisms in their habitats. Haeckel first used the term in 1869, defining ecology as the study of the physical and biological environment and its changes, and of their effects on other organisms. Accordingly, ecological studies proceed in two complementary parts: examining the characteristics of the environment surrounding living organisms, and examining their responses to environmental factors. Unfortunately, ecological concepts have sometimes been misinterpreted in certain professions, reduced merely to solving immediate environmental problems and using local materials and species, and mistakenly treated as constraints on creative design. Compared with biological concepts that address relationships among an organism’s internal parts—akin to modern architecture’s focus on the object itself—ecology attends to reciprocal relations between living beings and their surroundings, thus underscoring the role of context and external conditions in the quality of buildings. Architectural design informed by ecological concepts yields a comprehensive understanding of the environment and can shape values and goals, altering design perspectives and methods. On this basis, the ecological designer emphasizes (Aminzadeh, 2003):

- designing to give meaning to place;
- deriving solutions from the environment;
- designing in response to environmental conditions and people;
- using public input in design;
- designing with nature;
- assessing the environmental effects of design.

Warnings intensified from the early 1960s: global warming, shortages of potable water, rising pollution, anxiety over future oil supplies, and species extinction together made ecological thinking imperative for the foreseeable future (Singari, 2003).

2–15 Environmental Design

Environmental design is not new. Some 350,000 years ago, Europe’s ancestors were compelled by cold climates to build shelters in limestone escarpments. Perforated envelopes provided adequate daylight and reduced winter heat loss. In Doha, perforated houses were built to admit daylight while preventing heat penetration into interiors. Scientific advances during the Renaissance led to the Industrial Revolution, enabling environmental engineers to provide rational comfort conditions in almost any building, regardless of climate. Much of the visual power of contemporary architecture stems from technology, yet it has also brought us to certain limits. The engineering systems associated with such architecture often demand large amounts of energy to overcome environmental problems in design. We therefore need approaches that reduce high fossil-fuel consumption while maintaining occupant comfort (Gonzalo, 2002).

2–15–2 Environmental Buildings

What humans build reflects their ideals and aspirations; hence architectural transformations display human life and thought. Architecture appears as a mirror of human life and, because humans participate in its creation and development, it is related to various sciences and technologies. Thus, architecture is a philosophical category, the outcome of political decisions, a geographical phenomenon, and influenced by many sciences such as biology and ecology. Viewing architecture as a living organism is an old interpretation; however, such a concept drew greater attention in the early nineteenth century when the term “biology” became established as the “science of life” by Lamarck (Aminzadeh, 2003).

Environmental buildings are designed to benefit from favorable landscapes and climates and to ameliorate those aspects that are undesirable. This approach attends not only to the creation of comfortable interior spaces but also to the exterior design of buildings. Green spaces

in urban design and around private buildings influence microclimate and reduce outdoor temperatures.

Below is a summary of general principles that must be considered in the design of environmental buildings. The design rules for appropriate forms, street layouts, and environmental buildings—as well as for private buildings—should be followed. None of these principles may be ignored, and an appropriate combination is required for each site.

In general, buildings are comparable to animals. In cold weather they need an energy source to keep indoor air at a desirable level, and they also require a strategy to prevent the loss of warm air. In bears, this is achieved through a fur covering; in buildings, the analogous covering is thermal insulation. Heat loss associated with ventilation also requires specific rules, and most of our efforts aim to optimize control and maintenance techniques.

In hot weather, when outdoor temperatures are very high, more heat enters interior spaces. If this heat can be absorbed by the building fabric, peak temperatures will be reduced. If nighttime ventilation is possible, the heat absorbed by the fabric will be released when the air is cooler. What, then, should be done? (Gonzalo, 2002)

2–15–2 Five Principles in Environmental Architecture

Five principles of environmental architecture (Thomas Fisher):

1. **Healthy interiors:** Every possible measure must ensure that structural systems and materials do not emit pollutants and harmful gases into indoor spaces; indoor air should be kept clean and fresh by filters and plants.
2. **Energy efficiency:** Every possible measure must ensure minimal building energy consumption; heating, cooling, and lighting systems should employ methods and products that reduce demand.
3. **Ecological materials:** Every possible measure must produce and use building materials with the least environmental damage. If wood is used, forests must not be degraded; other materials and their use should not be based on environmental destruction and pollution.
4. **Environmental form:** Every possible measure must provide a site design appropriate to region and climate so as to optimize ecological performance—based on recycling and energy efficiency—and create a harmonious relationship between inhabitants and nature.

5. **Good design:** Every possible measure must consider the building's durability, efficiency, and beauty in relation to energy use, circulation, building form, building services, and construction technology, as well as symbolic relationships with history, site, and architectural principles, so that after completion it is low-consumption, simple, and elegant.

2–15–3 Environmental Design Strategies

The most important change in design method is to consider the building as a whole. From this perspective, we must examine site, form, materials, and structure so as to reduce energy consumption while maintaining occupant comfort. The importance of daylight is clear. Natural light is crucial, and the use of solar energy is highly valuable. Building design should provide adequate light whenever the sun is above the horizon, while avoiding glare and excessive heat. Accordingly, façade design and ventilation are key elements of a successful strategy. To achieve this goal, we need to develop economical triple-glazed windows with automated blinds to control solar radiation throughout the day (author).

2–16 Nature in Architecture

Attention to nature in architecture began in the nineteenth century. John Ruskin drew architects' attention to the harmonic; balanced order found in nature. William Morris called for a return to life in green suburbs so that nature might be better enjoyed. Some architects, seeking to connect and harmonize human beings with the natural environment through architectural space, turned to natural materials and, in some cases, vernacular methods; Frank Lloyd Wright and Hassan Fathy may be counted among them. After the energy crisis, adapting architectural space to the natural environment received greater attention, and **eco-tech** architecture gradually replaced high-tech forms that had been favored since the 1990s (Sultan-Zadeh, 2003). Nature is inspiring, informative, and a prominent basis for comparison (Lashgari, 2003). Nature can be used as a model at different levels (Jan Kaplický, 2003). In general, organic forms are more effective than artificial, human-made forms.

2–17 An Iranian Version of Sustainable Development

Avoidance of waste and extravagance; the use of local materials; appropriate choice of colors and forms; attention to diversity and methods of utilizing natural resources; selection of suitable energy sources; integration of the spiritual and material dimensions of life as the foundation and overarching frame for human activity and its outcomes; a sense of human

responsibility toward objects and spaces to encourage their protection and optimal use; attention to the collective spirit rather than individualism and self-display—these and many other characteristics may be considered the main features of an Iranian version of sustainable development (Taghizadeh, 2000).

Study of the traditional architecture of historical Iranian cities shows, first, that these cities may be regarded as outstanding examples of land improvement, and second, that in this improvement the best methods of accessing tools and materials, as well as the most appropriate ways of using them, were selected. By correctly understanding natural elements and their interrelationships, recognizing the principles and laws governing them, and appreciating their role in sustaining human life, Iranians created environments and spaces balanced and suited to the conditions required for life. The following are among such features (Naghizadeh, 2000):

- The hierarchy among domains (public, semi-public, semi-private, private) provided an appropriate degree of security—even from prying eyes—for residents.
- The adjacency and appropriate relationship of diverse elements with different material and spiritual functions expressed the unity of human life.
- The gathering of natural elements according to specific geometric rules and their integration with human-made elements produced one of the most notable garden traditions in the world, of which Iranians were the pioneers.
- Iranian architecture has always stood as an index of the artistry of its creators in forming desirable living environments.
- A brief review shows that, in regulating environmental conditions in buildings, the most sustainable and clean methods were used—methods regarded as integral parts of architecture rather than extraneous add-ons.
- The materials used in Iranian architecture possessed distinctive qualities: their production did not impose environmental degradation; moreover, the waste and debris from buildings at the end of their useful life did not harm nature and were readily reabsorbed.
- Proper orientation of buildings provided the best basis for exploiting energy or protecting inhabitants from adverse climatic conditions.
- Beyond meeting material criteria related to energy, natural resources, and efficiency, Iranian architecture also possessed features that significantly contributed to the expression of a sustainable, elevating spiritual life.

- For centuries in Iran, all buildings were constructed with regard to climate and environmental conditions. Sun, wind, humidity, landforms, and, in general, climatic and geographical conditions had a direct effect on our traditional architecture in different regions. With the advent of modern architecture and, especially, the use of mechanical systems, however, the role of climate in buildings gradually diminished (Battle McCarthy Consulting Engineers, 2006).

2–17–1 Iranian Architecture and Sustainability

In terms of sustainability, the architecture of this land’s past—both in its view of human–environment relations and in its practical solutions—offers a valuable field for inquiry and has the potential to inform decision-making in contemporary architecture. Considering its fundamental characteristics, at least the following may be noted (Ahmadi, 2007):

1. Iranian architecture is deeply symbolic and meaningful. Because its foundations are drawn from nature and its forces (light, water, wind, and earth), these matters are regarded at the highest level.
2. It is strongly text-oriented, earth-centered, and inseparable from its environment.
3. It is modest and sincere.
4. It exhibits logical economy alongside complexity.

The use of wind (airflow) for natural ventilation—through specific architectural devices—has long played a significant role in tempering indoor air in Iranian buildings, and today attracts serious professional attention; studies are underway or have been completed on its appropriate contemporary application (Taghizadeh, 2000). In contrast to traditional Iranian works, contemporary Iranian architecture—by focusing on material and economic aspects (profit-making) and neglecting the wholeness of human life—has come into conflict with principles that may be termed the foundations of sustainable development. Analysis of the governing principles of the aforementioned architecture shows that its salient feature was a humane, peaceful coexistence with nature—traceable in the appropriate, optimal use of natural resources accompanied by minimal environmental degradation.

2–17–2 The Manifestation of a Sustainable Spiritual Life and Iranian Architecture

In this regard, several key issues merit consideration, including: maintaining balance in attending simultaneously to human spiritual and material needs as the primary basis for equilibrium

in the use of natural resources; balance in generating various forms of environmental pollution in relation to the environment's capacity for absorption; balance between the built environment and nature and the spiritual-psychological and physical attributes of human beings; balance in the use of available energy sources so that the equilibrium present in nature is not disrupted; and commitment to devising methods for using natural energies such as sunlight and heat, wind movement, geothermal heat, wave motion, hydropower, and the like (Naghizadeh, 2000).

2-17-3 Elements of Iranian Architecture

Windcatchers functioned as an effective means of cooling interiors. Central courtyards consistently provided shaded surfaces; their depressed levels trapped cool air. The presence of water and vegetation within central courtyards helped temper the microclimate. The north and south iwans of the courtyard effectively supplied and defined two domains for summer and winter use. Wall and roof thickness minimized winter heat loss and summer heat gain. Dome roofs—with their material and color—reduced solar penetration. Appropriate dimensions admitted the required daylight and energy into the interior while preventing energy loss (author) (Fig. 2-3).

Figure 20-3

Iranian architects identified forms and employed them in their works to increase shading on surfaces. These forms, while appropriately addressing structural and technical issues, helped balance and protect interiors from external heat and cold, thereby reducing the need for additional energy. As noted, the regulation of indoor environmental conditions relied on maximal use of appropriate renewable energies (wind, sun, and water). In exterior and public spaces,

protection against the harsh desert climate and summer heat was provided by shade cast by high walls or trees (author).

2–17–4 Contemporary Iranian Architecture and Sustainable Development

With respect to the relationship between sustainable development, contemporary Iranian architecture, and Iranian culture, the transformations in Iran’s architecture and urbanism show that with the introduction of foreign ideas and models—and their imitation and repetition without evaluation—the programs and plans for urban development, and consequently the relationship between humans, nature, and the urban fabric, moved in a direction contrary to the past and, even economically, proceeded without reliance on theoretical bases derived from the society’s beliefs, needs, and realities. This phenomenon has altered the environment and increasingly distanced it from sustainable development. In many respects, contemporary architecture stands in opposition to the principles of national culture and sustainable development; a few examples follow (Taghizadeh, 2000):

- As noted, contemporary Iranian architecture is strongly influenced by foreign architecture; this contradicts the essential principle of respecting national culture and providing a model of sustainable development aligned with Iranian culture.
- Relative neglect of unity and wholeness in architecture and the urban fabric, and of the harmony and proportion that must exist among their parts, is one manifestation of opposition to sustainable development.
- In a cultural and functional shift from *architecture* toward *building production*—and, consequently, in urbanism from creating collective living spaces toward mass housing production—profit and economic return have become primary aims.
- Because of the focus on revenue, many usable buildings are demolished and replaced with more, smaller housing units, without any program—indeed, without even the intention—to provide for the cultural, educational, medical, religious, retail, and transport needs of the increased population. Another negative outcome is the dumping of large volumes of construction debris in nature, which cannot easily be absorbed and imposes heavy costs. Energy consumption for various purposes is among the most serious problems to which contemporary architecture has contributed.
- In most contemporary Iranian works, few of the above principles—well established in traditional Iranian architecture and in the criteria of sustainable development—are properly observed. What clearly stands out is the economic, revenue-driven aspect, especially in the short term.

In conclusion, although contemporary architecture focuses on the material dimension of human life and, consequently, on maximizing economic (profitable) returns, by neglecting the spiritual dimension of life it loses comprehensiveness and unity and disregards the governing principles of the natural order. By damaging the regulated system of life on earth, it will not succeed even economically in the long run.

2–18 Green Architecture

A green approach refers to a holistic attitude toward building design that encompasses all building resources, materials, and the fuels required by users. If sustainable design is pursued, the production of a green building engages with numerous issues, incompatibilities, and needs. Every designer must attend to environmental concepts; four are particularly important (Soflaei, 2006):

- Reducing energy consumption.
- Reducing external pollution and environmental degradation.
- Recovering embodied energy and reducing depletion of natural resources.
- Reducing indoor environmental pollution.

2–18–1 Green Building

Architect William McDonough describes the spirit of a green building as follows (ibid.):

- Meeting all water and energy needs within the site.
- Fitting the site and climate and accounting for changing environmental conditions.
- Avoiding pollution and the production of wastes that are not useful to other building or environmental processes.
- Promoting the health and well-being of occupants as a healthy ecosystem.
- Using systems that are maximally efficient and comfortable.
- Strengthening the health and diversity of the local ecosystem.
- Being beautiful and inviting to human imagination.

A green building will use the minimum possible energy while providing most of the embodied and required energy for its construction. Ideally, a building supplies its energy through renewable fuels—such as plant-based oils—and solar energy. Where possible, it should generate more energy than it consumes so it can supply neighboring buildings. The structure should be flexible so that it has a long life (Soflaei, 2006).

What makes a green building?

A green building occupies a high place in environmental health and resource conservation over its life cycle. These basic requirements—principles and relationships among building design, economy, profitability, durability, and delight—are further developed and refined. Green design emphasizes a set of relationships among environment, resources, and occupant health, including:

- Reducing the use of destructive materials.
- Protecting renewable energies and scarce materials.
- Reducing life-cycle ecological impacts and the consumption of environmental resources.
- Using renewable energies and natural, durable materials.
- Protecting and conserving air, water, soil, and local vegetation and wildlife.
- Supporting pedestrian and bicycle networks and other non-fuel transport options.

Most green buildings are higher in quality, have longer service lives, and cost less to build and maintain, while also satisfying occupants regarding development standards. Buyers and tenants prefer such buildings and are often willing to pay a premium for future benefits. What seems surprising to many is unfamiliarity with this type of design, since well-designed green buildings often have costs equal to or less than conventional buildings. Green architecture guides building design toward optimal energy use and the application of recycled materials in construction (Aminzadeh, 2003).

2-18-2 Green Roofs

This idea was the innovation of Kazuyoshi Kojima, age 25, to achieve lower temperatures in Japanese cities. Kojima says: rooftop gardens help absorb heat and lower indoor temperatures. We used to set air conditioners to 30°C and the air was still warm. Now, thanks to the rooftop garden, 27–28°C feels acceptable. Likewise, in winter, buildings need only one hour of heating and the remaining warmth stays in the space; therefore, energy costs decrease significantly. Kojima believes this does not require great expense. He says: “*Gardening on the roof is something anyone can do—if one simply puts one’s mind to it.*” (Greening the Roofs of Tokyo, 2003).

2–19 Necessity of Using Natural Energies (Renewable and New)

Given the environmental harms associated with fossil-fuel use, employing renewable energy sources is a fundamental topic for a responsible future energy policy (Sarabi, 2004).

Energy supply and demand have become one of the most important global issues, such that the world will be seriously engaged with it through the end of the twentieth century and beyond. Fossil energies such as oil, gas, and coal will eventually run out, and with their depletion, human civilization—which directly depends on energy—will face a new and major challenge. This has led industrially developed countries to pursue, with utmost seriousness, the use of other energies available in nature, especially new energies. The use of solar, wind, wave, geothermal, hydrogen, biomass, and other sources—known as new energies—requires extensive study and research (Wind Energy, Third Report).

The sun is not only a vast energy source in itself; it is also the origin of life and the source of all other energies. Scientific estimates indicate that about 6,000 million years have passed since the birth of this fiery sphere, and that every second 4.2 million tons of the sun's mass are converted into energy. Considering that the sun's mass is roughly 333,000 times that of the earth, this luminous body may be regarded as a vast energy source for the next five billion years (Solar Energy, First Report).

Solar energy is the origin of fossil fuels and maintains the world's average temperature at about 15 °C. Sunlight can replace high-grade electrical lighting energy: one watt of natural light can substitute for more than three watts of primary energy used for fluorescent lighting, and even more for replacing the harmful light of tungsten lamps (Gonzalo, 2002)

2–19–1 Applications of Solar Energy

Solar energy is a free, clean source of energy devoid of destructive environmental effects, used by humans in various ways since ancient times. The recent energy crisis has compelled countries to address energy differently; among the responses, substituting fossil energy with solar energy—to reduce and economize energy consumption, control supply and demand, and reduce pollutant emissions—has been widely welcomed.

Since every form of energy on earth ultimately derives its energy from the sun, and since in many cases—especially in buildings (when solar energy is used)—there is no need for long-distance transmission networks, solar energy may be called the most suitable, cleanest, most

reliable, most accessible, and most independent form of energy. If the technology is localized, solar energy can play a valuable role in a country's industrial independence. Moreover, due to Iran's geographic position, the country has the potential for self-sufficiency in energy (Taghizadeh, 2000).

Today solar energy is utilized through various systems for diverse purposes, including:

Use of solar thermal energy for domestic, industrial, and power-plant applications.

Direct conversion of solar radiation into electricity via photovoltaic equipment.

In general, solar energy uses can be categorized as follows:

1-1 Electricity supply using photovoltaics.

2-1 Electricity supply using solar thermal power.

2) Solar cooling.

3) Solar cookers.

4) Solar desalination.

5) Solar heating:

1-5 Domestic hot water using solar water heaters.

2-5 Heating for residential and commercial spaces.

3-5 Supplying hot water in industrial processes and heat for specific operations.

4-5 Pool heating.

5-5 Seasonal water-storage tanks.

6-5 District heating (Solar Energy, First Report).

2-19-2 Application of Solar Energy in Architecture and Urbanism

Heating and cooling buildings with solar energy was a new idea proposed in the 1930s and achieved notable progress within less than a decade. By adding an absorption refrigeration system to solar systems, in addition to domestic hot-water production and heating, these systems can also provide cooling in warm seasons (Solar Energy, First Report).

2-19-3 Advantages and Disadvantages of Using Solar Energy

As a natural energy source, solar energy has the following advantages (www.ifco.ir):

- Clean and non-polluting (eliminates greenhouse-gas emissions, including carbon dioxide).
- Unlimited.
- Free.
- Reduces consumption of fossil fuels.
- Avoids risks of poisoning, fire, explosion, and electric shock associated with gas, liquid and solid fuels, and electricity.

The principal disadvantage is the high initial cost; these systems have not yet become economical globally. Extensive efforts are underway to reduce costs.

2–19–4 Use of Solar Energy in Iran

Iran lies between latitudes 25° and 40° N, in a region among the highest in the world for solar energy receipt. Annual solar radiation in Iran is estimated at 1,800–2,200 kWh/m², above the global average.

Solar heating for domestic hot water in Iran has been implemented through two systems:

1. Domestic solar water heaters.
2. Rural public solar bath water heaters.

2–19–5 The Photovoltaic Phenomenon

The direct conversion of radiant energy into electrical energy is called the photovoltaic phenomenon. Any system that uses the photovoltaic effect (direct conversion of radiation to electricity) is called a photovoltaic system.

A panel that converts solar radiation into electricity is called a solar cell or battery; solar cells are mainly made of silicon. A set of several cells forming a panel is called a module or panel; a set of photovoltaic panels is called a solar array.

The electric current from photovoltaic panels is direct current (DC). Solar cells are merely converters of solar radiation into electricity; they do not store energy. Energy storage in these systems is provided by electrochemical batteries. The current–voltage characteristic of panels varies with constant temperature and changing irradiance, and also with constant irradiance and changing temperature (Renewable Energy Organization of Iran (SUNA)).

The typical service life of photovoltaic panels is about 25 (20 to 30) years.

Types of solar cells include: monocrystalline, polycrystalline, and amorphous.

The three main parts of photovoltaic systems are:

- Solar panels.
- The intermediary section.
- The load (consumer).

The function of solar panels is to supply the electrical power required by the system; because the panels provide the needed electricity, the system is termed photovoltaic. The intermediary or power-matching section controls and matches the electrical power from the panels to the load.

Main applications of photovoltaic systems include:

Stand-alone systems independent of the main grid.

- Grid-connected systems.
- Hybrid systems.

Key advantages and disadvantages of photovoltaic systems include:

Advantages:

- No need for the national grid.
- No fuel requirement.
- Environmentally compatible; does not pollute.
- No noise pollution.
- No water required for electricity generation.

Disadvantages:

- High initial capital cost.
- Dependence on variations in solar radiation during the day and across months.

Although these systems have not yet become economical worldwide, specialists are working to reduce costs and make them viable. However, in some locations—where distance from the national grid is great, fuel delivery is impossible, access is difficult, or fuel costs are high—these systems are economical, such as:

- Off-grid villages.
- Refrigerated vehicles transporting food, especially in African countries with suitable insolation.
- Off-grid recreational camps.

- Telecommunication centers, meteorological stations, etc., located in inaccessible, un-electrified areas.

Types of collectors used in solar water heaters:

- Flat plate collectors (Flat plate collectors – EPC).
- Compound parabolic collectors.
- Evacuated tube collectors (Evacuated Tube Collectors – ETC).
- These collectors are typically installed in fixed positions and do not require solar tracking.

2–19–6 Use of Solar Energy in Iran

Iran lies between 25° and 40° north latitude and is located in a region that ranks among the highest in the world for solar energy reception. Annual solar radiation in Iran is estimated at 1,800–2,200 kWh/m², which is above the global average.

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2–19–7 The Photovoltaic Phenomenon

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- Hybrid systems.

The principal advantages and disadvantages of photovoltaic systems are as follows:

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- Off-grid villages.

- Refrigerated vehicles transporting perishable foods, especially in African countries with strong insolation.
- Off-grid recreational camps.
- Telecommunication centers, meteorological stations, and similar facilities in inaccessible areas without electricity.

Solar collectors used in water heaters:

- Flat-plate collectors (Flat Plate Collectors – FPC).
- Compound parabolic collectors (CPC).
- Evacuated tube collectors (Evacuated Tube Collectors – ETC).
- These collectors are typically installed in fixed positions and do not require solar tracking.

2–20 How Do Solar Water Heaters Work?

The most important part of any solar water-heating (SWH) system is its array of collectors, which absorb solar energy and convert it to heat. The heat received is absorbed by a working fluid (water, antifreeze solution, or air) passing through the collector. This heat can be used directly or stored in a thermal reservoir for later use. Because system components are constantly exposed to weather, they must be protected against freezing or excessive temperatures when demand is low.

In solar water-heater systems, domestic water is heated either directly by passing through the collector (direct-circulation systems) or indirectly via a heat exchanger, itself heated in a closed loop by the collector fluid (indirect-circulation systems). The working fluid moves either naturally (passive) or by forced circulation (active). Natural circulation occurs through thermosiphon action, while forced circulation uses a pump. Apart from thermosiphon and integral collector-storage systems, other solar water-heating systems are controlled by differential thermostats.

Five types of solar systems can be used for domestic or sanitary hot water: thermosiphon, integral collector–storage, forced circulation, indirect, and air systems. The first two are passive; the other three are active because they employ a pump or fan to circulate the working fluid. To prevent collector freezing, direct systems use recirculation or drain-down; indirect systems use drain-back.

All these systems can be economically advantageous; depending on the alternative fuel, payback periods range from about 4 years (electricity) to 7 years (diesel). Payback varies by country according to economic indicators such as inflation and fuel prices. Today, solar collectors are widely used worldwide for solar water heaters.

2–21 Hydropower

Hydropower is among the oldest and most developed renewable-energy technologies. Three thousand years ago, waterwheels provided the first alternative to muscle power for milling grain and moving water in irrigation systems (Walisiewicz, 2005).

Iran's permanent, large rivers make the construction of dams and hydropower plants feasible; for example, Japanese studies on the Karun River confirmed the possibility of constructing 13 dams (Feizi, 2003).

2–21–2 Disadvantages of Large Hydropower Plants

Although hydropower is clean and emits no pollutants during operation, large-scale expansion presents obvious problems. The immense reservoir created by projects like the Yangtze scheme would displace more than three million people, submerge 100 cities, and destroy many valuable habitats. Dams concentrate pollutants carried by upstream cities and disrupt important activities downstream. For example, the Aswan High Dam in Egypt, completed in 1964, severely disrupted the eastern Mediterranean fishing industry (Walisiewicz, 2005).

2–21–3 Tidal Energy

The daily rise and fall of tides provide a vast, clean, largely untapped energy resource—estimated by some at up to 1,000 GW (Walisiewicz, 2005).

Two engineering approaches exist. The first uses arrays of large underwater turbines, like windmills, placed where tidal currents are strong (channels between islands or around headlands). Such sites are rare but sufficient to contribute significantly to future energy needs. The second approach resembles conventional hydropower: large barrages trap incoming tides and then release the water through turbine arrays.

2–21–4 Wave Energy

Waves form when wind moves the surface of the open ocean, creating local breaking waves whose turbulent energy dissipates and propagates long distances—thousands of kilometers—as swell. Before reaching shallow waters, waves lose nearly 60 percent of their energy through sea-surface friction (Walisiewicz, 2005).

Harnessing wave energy is fundamentally harder than using river flow. Waves do not move uniformly in one direction, and devices designed for normal sea conditions must also withstand severe storms. Nevertheless, engineering solutions continue to advance; devices fall broadly into floating and fixed types.

2–23 Geothermal Energy (Energy from the Earth’s Interior)

We all stand atop an immense boiler. Thousands of kilometers beneath us, heat released by the natural decay of radioactive elements keeps our planet’s interior at around 7,000 °C (Waliszewicz, 2005).

There is an urgent need to develop technology and capacity for geothermal energy, an inexhaustible earthly resource that can replace fossil fuels and provide a secure solution for the future. Geothermal energy offers abundant “clean” heat and power (very low or no greenhouse-gas emissions), high availability (about 95 percent), and domestic production (reducing oil consumption). Resources range from shallow areas where the distance from surface to heat source is small, to hot water and rocks several miles deep, and even higher temperatures near molten rock (magma). Geothermal energy can be converted to heat and electricity. Current uses include heat pumps, direct-use heating, and power plants.

The Romans piped underground steam to heat their homes; in many cities—such as Reykjavík, Iceland—geothermal energy heats residences, offices, and factories. The first geothermal power plant began operating in 1913 at Larderello in northern Italy. Today, geothermal energy is among the most promising renewable resources.

2–24 Biogas Energy

Biogas is a by-product of anaerobic decomposition of organic materials such as agricultural residues, animal and human waste, wood remains, bark, and similar matter. Also called “biogas” or “marsh gas,” it is a mixture of gases produced by anaerobic decomposition of organic compounds: roughly 50–60% methane, 35–45% carbon dioxide, 1–2% nitrogen, 5–10% hydrogen sulfide, and trace oxygen (Amirnejad, 2003).

2–24–1 History of Biogas Use

The first practical application dates to the eighteenth century, when Paris Street lighting used animal waste (from carriage horses). Widespread use followed World War II in European municipal wastewater treatment plants. In recent decades, due to energy shortages and price

increases, almost all municipal plants in Western Europe have installed biogas systems and supply a major part of their own energy.

2–24–2 Advantages and Disadvantages of Biogas Energy

Biogas can be used as fuel for cooking in rural communities, for lighting, or for mechanical power and engines. Besides supplying energy, it prevents the dispersion of plant residues and animal and human waste in the environment, thereby reducing pollution. The digested residue (sludge), when properly processed, becomes high-quality compost that significantly improves agricultural soil fertility.

Overall benefits include:

- A local, renewable energy source.
- Improved industrial and domestic safety; economic viability.
- Better air quality and reduced odors.
- Reduced emissions of greenhouse gases harmful to the ozone layer.
- Economic growth and energy security.
- Centralized collection of organic wastes, preventing dispersion.
- Use of produced biomass as safe, reliable fertilizer.

Main drawbacks:

1. Shortage of specialized personnel compared with other methods.
2. Ash remaining from burning residues can acidify surrounding soils.

2–25 New Methods in Sustainable Architecture

2–25–1 The Concept of Bionics in Architecture

“Bionics”—from *biology* and *technics*—meaning bio-cybernetics or the application of nature’s artificial organs, was first used by the American scientist Jack E. Steele in 1959. Bionics, or the study of living systems, is recognized today as one of the three leading sciences (IT, Nano, Bionic). For centuries, humans have lived in close relation with nature and drawn inspiration from it—e.g., bird flight inspiring countless flying-machine designs. One of the earliest architectural uses of natural models was Joseph Paxton’s Crystal Palace at the 1851 London Exhibition. In essence, bionics and bionic architecture derive technical inspiration from the structures, behaviors, and communications of living organisms; they develop systems whose foundations mirror living systems. The term embraces all specialists who seek solutions to

technical problems by learning from nature. Since every living being today is the product of two billion years of evolution, nature has ruthlessly eliminated what did not suit its purposes; this vast experience can be applied to building machines that operate in life-like ways (Quarterly of the Qazvin Province Construction Engineering Organization, 2012).

2-25-2 Bionic Forms

2-25-2-1 Phyllotactic Towers

All residential towers built to date—from the simplest box forms of the late nineteenth century to the most complex of the early twenty-first—share a major shortcoming: residents do not have open sky above their own yard, because apartments lack courtyards. This common feature has numerous negative psychological effects, especially on children. Architecturally, the problem arises because in almost all residential towers built up to 2012, each floor slab is the ceiling of the floor below, making private courtyards impossible. (Fig. 2-1)

Figure 2-0-1

The courtyard is an essential, age-old component of dwelling, yet in residential towers it has been forgotten—an intentional omission by capitalist thinking, wrongly blamed on scientists and architects (Quarterly of the Qazvin Province Construction Engineering Organization, 2012). A house without a courtyard is not a house but an apartment unit, and an apartment unit is not a natural place for human life because it ignores the courtyard—the result of millennia of habitation.

In phyllotactic towers, floor slabs are not shared; this is the fundamental difference between phyllotaxis and Le Corbusier's Domino system. Each apartment has its own open private courtyard; each unit can thus be called a house (ibid.)

Urbanism today faces a key question in sustainability: how can we have a compact, high-density city while maintaining humane living—homes with courtyards and gardens, and pleasant communal and semi-public spaces in towers? The proposed model seeks to resolve this contradiction as far as possible.

Requiring a courtyard for every unit leads to another outcome: the surface-area-to-volume ratio of these towers reaches a maximum, enabling maximal benefit from natural energies. Studies show that leaf arrangements on plant stems enable maximal capture of natural energies; these patterns, called *phyllotaxis*, are used in phyllotactic towers to organize dwellings around a central core. By employing different phyllotactic patterns, horizontal and vertical spacing between units can be adjusted according to geographic region and climate, adapting tower density by height to diverse climates. Binary, ternary, and quaternary patterns are among the architectural phyllotactic configurations (Quarterly of the Qazvin Province Construction Engineering Organization, 2012).

Nearly all parts of phyllotactic towers have direct access to sunlight and open air. Because of the phyllotactic arrangement around the core, units cast minimal shade on one another—just as leaves do on plants. In sum, each dwelling has its own open private courtyard and can receive maximal sunlight—one of the primary energy sources for future sustainable architecture and urbanism (ibid.).

2-25-2-2 LAVA's Bionic Tower

The concept of a bionic tower explores architectural and natural strategies that merge to create an inhabitable structure from the ground up. Drawing on organizational resources of biological ecosystems, the design responds from the smallest unit to system-wide information. Using parametric modeling of behavioral logic, the system is continuously optimized. This LAVA project, based on biological morphology and inspired by nature, seeks—through advanced design techniques—to achieve a lightweight, efficient, and magnificent structure (www.memarinews.com) (Fig. 2-2).

Figure 0-2

2-25-2-3 Taiwan Bionic Tower

Concurrent with the celebration of the centennial of Taiwan's independence, the world's most advanced skyscraper, employing the principles of bionic architecture, will be inaugurated. Designed by Vincent Callebaut, the bionic skyscraper has been conceived to honor local building traditions and to symbolize Taiwan's dynamism in the economic, social, and cultural spheres. This tower stands as an emblem for the cities of the future and a model for new ways of living, innovation, culture, and an international construction paradigm in the twenty-first century. The use of innovative designs and artificial curves are among the architectural and design features of the tower. This green tower showcases a system of vertical green gardens and the interaction between human and natural environments. The design marks a step toward sustainable development and the use of new, environmentally compatible energies—including solar and wind power (to supply 100% of electrical energy)—together with botany and biotechnology (www.memarinews.com) (Fig. 2-3).

Figure 2-3

The design of this tower maintains that standards far exceeding those of existing green buildings can be achieved, and that new dimensions in the relationship between humans and nature can be discovered. The tower is conceived with overarching objectives such as raising awareness of climate change and the need for environmental protection; positioning Taiwan as a global model in sustainable architecture; realizing fully self-sufficient, zero-carbon-dioxide buildings; reducing greenhouse-gas emissions; and ultimately supporting government policies for energy conservation (www.memarinews.com).

2–25–2–4 HYDRA TOWER Residential Tower

The power of hydrogen is an extraordinary alternative energy source, because it burns very cleanly, emitting only water vapor and heat—although, in truth, achieving the necessary technology takes time, and we currently expend considerable energy to produce hydrogen fuel. HYDRA Tower therefore appears to propose an architectural solution for hydrogen—or the most rational mode of action—by using electricity generated from lightning to split water molecules into hydrogen and oxygen. At the tip of the tower, a conically tapered helical outer protective sheath of graphene is installed. Graphene, a carbon-based material, is about 200 times stronger than steel and highly conductive to heat and electricity; it serves as an optimal skyward channel capable of receiving an extraordinary amount of electrical energy from the atmosphere (www.memarinews.com) (Fig. 2-4).

Figure 0-4

During lightning storms, the sharp, superconductive skin of the mast at the top of the tower transfers the captured electricity to a large battery bank at the tower's base. This energy is then used to split water into hydrogen gas through electrolysis. The tower's twisting form was inspired by Hydra, a simple freshwater organism. The project also includes a research center, housing, and recreational areas for the enjoyment of scientists and their families.

This skyscraper was designed in 2011 by architects Milos Vlastic, Vuk Djendjevic, Asa Lazovic, and Milica Samkovic, drawing on a skyscraper concept. It is intended for implementation in tropical regions—where some 70% of all lightning occurs (including areas such as Singapore, Central Florida, Venezuela, and Kifuka in the Democratic Republic of the Congo)—so that buildings can make optimal use of atmospheric electrical energy (www.memarinews.com).

2–26 Vertical Farms

Given the features of an indoor vertical farm, the nutrient content, temperature, humidity, air flow, and light can all be regulated. In this controlled environment, plants can be grown with minimal herbicides and pesticides. The key rationale is that these vertical landscapes not only curb greenhouse-gas emissions by eliminating the need to transport produce, but also prevent spoilage during transit. The greatest advantages of hydroponic cultivation include reducing problems of soil erosion and significantly lowering water consumption compared with conventional agriculture. However, as of now, no large-scale vertical farm has been constructed due to high costs and limited infrastructure (Chino, 2013).

3–27 Marina Residential Tower

The Marina residential tower in Chicago contributes significantly to the city’s environmental quality. Reimagined as an algae producer and carbon reducer with greenhouses capable of providing all of its own energy needs, the towers—built in 1962—require major retrofitting and energy-efficiency upgrades. The proposal by Influx Studio goes beyond conventional retrofit measures by adding a CO₂-scrubbing system at the top of the tower. Inside each building, an algae bioreactor, photovoltaics, vertical gardens, and rainwater harvesting are incorporated. This synergy allows the towers to be self-sustaining and turns them into a healthy, sustainable landmark in downtown Chicago (Chino, 2013).

Two carbon-scrubbing plants installed on the towers would capture CO₂ from the air, filter it, and release oxygen, thereby providing a valuable source to feed biomass production. Wind turbines atop the towers would generate electricity from wind and air currents. Algae bioreactors, located near the top of the towers and on one of the building’s ramps, would capture solar radiation and CO₂ from the scrubbers to produce biofuel for use in industry and vehicles. The ultimate result is a fully sustainable building that helps reduce the city’s ecological footprint (Chino, 2013).

3: Chapter Three:

Regulations and Standards for the Design of Residential
Towers

3–1 General Forms of High-Rise Buildings

In general, the design of high-rise buildings can be divided into two overall morphologies (Building and Housing Research Center, 2002):

- High-rise buildings with a central core design.
- High-rise buildings with a bar/linear design.

3–2 Open Spaces in Residential Towers

Constraints in large cities have led to the proliferation of residential complexes and a reduced share of private courtyards in contemporary architecture. Residential open space, in addition to providing daylight and natural ventilation for interiors, offers opportunities for closer contact with nature and for social interaction. Given the limited interior area of residential units and the traditional precedent of the courtyard in Iranian life, open space becomes a field for extending interior functions and linking inside and outside. A review and understanding of the current condition of open spaces can therefore inform more deliberate design of residential open spaces in the future.

Open spaces between residential buildings provide the setting that connects residents to nature and serves as leisure ground in everyday life. Historically, the courtyard was the primary and most accessible space for intimate contact with nature and the outdoors. Under present urban conditions, detached single-family living is generally unattainable, and contemporary dwellings, within current constraints, fail to meet many needs of Iranian life. In such circumstances, living in high-rise residential buildings with limited internal space creates a need for private residential open spaces to strengthen residents' sense of belonging (Einifar, 2010).

3–3 Residential Open Spaces

As the dimensions and spaces of the four-iwān house increased, it became impossible to roof the central area, which thus turned into a courtyard (Pirnia, 2008). In early houses, open space was placed at the center to ensure security and privacy and to provide seclusion (Pourdeihimi, 2003).

The courtyard is the principal open space of the house. Beyond the courtyard, a range of open spaces exists at different levels. Through intermediary spaces such as the Soffeh, Shārmī, and Tāromī, inside and outside are fused and extended (Haeri, 2009).

In some seasons many indoor functions—sleeping, dining, and entertaining—moved into the courtyard. The presence of trees and water in the courtyard was essential, such that the Iranian house has been described as containing an excerpt of paradise.

3–4 Connectivity of Open Spaces Across Blocks

High-rise residential complexes composed of multiple blocks can be analyzed not only by access type and interior spatial relations, but also by the arrangement and adjacency of open and built spaces. Common types include perimeter layouts, freestanding blocks, row blocks, and mixed combinations (Biddulph, 2007).

In residential towers, the freestanding arrangement is optimal for locating open space between buildings; beyond providing suitable mutual shading, it also creates improved views (author).

3–5 Standards for Open Spaces

In mass housing and tall-building complexes, independent of north–south parceling, a wide variety of open/closed adjacencies is possible. Under the Second Development Plan, developers constructing 30 or more units under one permit were classified as mass builders; under the Third Plan, this threshold was reduced to 10 units (Rafieian & Hadadan, 2007)

At present, under regulations for buildings above six stories in Tehran, all residential blocks on a site must observe the rule of adequate distance between buildings (at least half the height of each building), and their placement must avoid obstructing one another’s daylight access (Secretariat of the Supreme Council of Urban Planning and Architecture of Iran, 2004: 41). The general formula proposed for calculating required open space in such complexes—based on an environmental and urban-planning adjustment coefficient K_a —is as follows:

Open-space area = $(K_a \times \text{total gross floor area (excluding basement)} \times 42) \div (100 \times \text{number of floors})$

According to the “Guidelines for Controlling Building Density and Determining Site Coverage in Residential Zones,” the minimum open space per unit for buildings over nine stories or with at least 40 units is set at 40 m² (Secretariat of the Supreme Council of Urban Planning and Architecture of Iran, 2004).

3–6 Design of Elevated Courtyards

Residents' health is among the least-addressed issues in today's urban fabric; green towers now prioritize occupants' health. The building envelope and each floor should be designed as a protective skin that plays a decisive role in ventilating interior air (author).

Creating floor-specific courtyards in towers can substantially contribute to this goal. Designing green projecting terraces—using contemporary technologies and inventive schemes—can enhance quality of life for tower residents and positively affect mental health (ibid.).

3–7 Principal Factors for Environmental Control in High-Rise Residential Design

Environmental control in tall buildings can be achieved through various methods. The intensity of climatic impacts can be assessed and managed in several ways and, for residential towers, may be considered across four broad domains (ibid.).

3–7–1 Natural Factors

Natural factors have always served as valuable resources for humankind. Across history, humans have modified the natural environment to optimize it for their needs. Natural elements and forces play decisive roles in shaping the built environment; conversely, once created and occupied, the built environment influences human character, behavior, and functional systems. Properly leveraging these factors can establish optimal conditions in residential towers (author).

3–7–2 Climatic Conditions

Site climate has scale. Whatever the project sizes, the site's local climate governs the immediate context. Designers should configure buildings to maximize favorable conditions and mitigate adverse and uncomfortable aspects of climate. Among local factors, airflow and winds are strongly affected by the siting of tall buildings; this section examines those effects (ibid.).

3–8 Impacts of Climate-Responsive (Architectural) Design

3–8–1 The Effect of Form on a Building's Energy Performance

Form emerges through interaction with nature. A living organism depends on its capacity to respond to the environment for survival; relationships that ensure survival drive the creation and evolution of form. In our world, every new idea is rooted in discovering hidden aspects of nature revealed through observation and natural analogues.

3–9 Aerodynamic Building Forms

3–9–1 Characteristics of Wind Flow

To control wind in climate-responsive architecture, one must first understand the governing principles and then examine its effects on the environment and architectural space.

3–9–2 Wind Impacts on Occupants of Tall Buildings

Human tolerance to wind—indoors and outdoors—is a major consideration in high-rise design. Lateral motion at the tops of tall structures due to wind energy must be reduced to acceptable levels. Some residents experience motion-induced nausea and dizziness. Occupants perceive building sway; in such cases, disturbing sounds may arise from elevator movement, air leakage at windows, and wind noise around the building envelope.

Because of persistent turbulent winds on façades, balcony use is often impractical except on very calm days. Designers of residential towers must therefore attend to building form, appropriate façade articulation, and structural flexural controls.

3–9–3 Human Tolerance to Wind

Approximate thresholds of wind-speed tolerance:

- 1–2 km/h: negligible.
- 2–4 km/h: pleasant.
- 4–8 km/h: tolerable.
- 8–16 km/h: occasionally uncomfortable.
- ≥ 16 km/h: intolerable.

3–9–4 Governing Principles of Wind Flow

Effective architectural wind control requires adequate information on local wind speeds and patterns. Although wind speed and direction within urban fabric, streets, and interiors depend on local winds, they are often strongly modified by natural features and the built environment.

3–9–5 Changes in Wind Speed

On encountering obstacles, wind speed decreases according to obstacle density (plan and height). Wind speed increases with elevation and distance from the ground; thus, wind speeds are higher at upper levels of towers and can be beneficially harnessed for ventilation and energy systems.

3–10 Creation of High- and Low-Pressure Zones Around Towers

When wind strikes an obstacle, a high-pressure zone forms upwind, with low-pressure zones at the sides and downwind. If the obstacle has windward openings but no outlets, air will not pass through; with outlets, air enters from the high-pressure side and exits toward low pressure (Razjooyan, 2000).

3–11 Stack-Driven Ventilation (Atria in Towers)

Ventilation by convection (air displacement) establishes airflow from higher to lower pressure zones. Openings must therefore be placed in areas with differing temperature and pressure. This flow is gentler than wind-driven ventilation—more of a breeze. In residential towers, this method can provide natural ventilation for shared spaces (Rah Shahr International Group, 2011).

3–12 Effects of Wind Flow on Building Form

To reduce wind effects, the windward face should be minimized or shielded. To increase wind utilization, façades should face open spaces and incorporate multiple openings. In low-rise buildings and towers in windy regions, the windward façade should avoid sharp corners and favor convex shapes to guide flow to the sides. Stepped massing also helps wind “leap” over the structure (*ibid.*).

3–13 Effects of Wind Flow on Building Orientation

To limit wind pressure on tall buildings, the narrow face should be oriented toward the prevailing wind; in other words, the windward frontage should be as small as possible (Rah Shahr International Group, 2011).

3–14 Effects of Wind Flow on Façade Characteristics

Façade configuration—especially in tall buildings—is strongly shaped by wind. Balconies on windward corners, curved surfaces, and even the form and operation of openings are wind-dependent. Proper façade design can reduce aerodynamic loads on the structure and simultaneously enable effective natural ventilation for occupants (*ibid.*).

3–15 Form-Making to Improve Air Circulation

Building shape governs the amplitude and path of wind. Avoiding disruption of natural wind patterns is crucial yet difficult, since construction readily alters wind speed, direction, and pressure. Appropriate form thus gains importance. Once designers understand local climate, they

can select and compare forms suited to it. Achieving a suitable form requires skill in steering wind around the building. This demands prior knowledge of wind modifications around structures and their consequences.

Horizontal air movements dissipate temperature, humidity, and pressure differences across the horizontal layers of the atmosphere, restoring equilibrium. With appropriate form-based moderators, the scope and flexibility of wind can be managed. Because wind speed affects form selection, employing suitable geometries—curvilinear and faceted—can both reduce structural dynamic loads and promote internal air circulation for occupant comfort (author).

3–16 Mechanical Systems

3–16–1 Cooling via Evaporative Refrigeration

Recent components inspired by the Iranian windcatcher have been designed to harness airflow; in some variants, the duct doubles as a light well. Sometimes a fan—powered by solar energy—is added to the ventilation/light shaft to boost air movement (Rah Shahr International Group, 2011).

Beyond ventilation and sensible cooling (by replacing warm air with cool air), wind can be combined with evaporative cooling to accelerate and intensify cooling. Evaporation requires heat; most of it is drawn from air adjacent to wetted surfaces. When wind passes over these surfaces, its heat is consumed by evaporation and the airstream is cooled. Ventilating interiors with this cooled air increases the cooling effect (*ibid.*).

3–16–2 Absorption-Based Cooling Systems

3–16–2–1 Use of Desiccants in Cooling and Air-Conditioning

Much of Iran has a hot–dry climate, and cooling systems are used during most months, consuming a large share of produced energy. High-efficiency cooling methods can therefore play an important role in reducing consumption. Among these, absorption/desiccant cooling has gained attention and is increasingly feasible (Pahlavanzadeh, 2006).

Desiccant cooling systems—solid or liquid—reduce energy use; the extent depends on parameters such as desiccant type (solid/liquid), system configuration (ventilation, rotary flow), ambient temperature and humidity, cooling cycle employed, room setpoints, desiccant regeneration temperature, process-to-regeneration air ratios, and desiccant-contact air ratios (*ibid.*).

3–16–2–2 Principles of Desiccant Cooling

Desiccant cooling is based on removing moisture from incoming air by forcing it across a desiccant, then sensibly cooling the airstream to the target temperature. For continuous operation, the absorbed moisture must be removed from the desiccant (regeneration). In general, the system comprises three stages:

- Moisture removal by a desiccant.
- Sensible cooling to the required supply temperature.
- A heat source for desiccant regeneration (Pahlavanzadeh, 2006).

3–16–2–3 Desiccant Materials

Desiccants—physical or chemical—absorb and release water vapor based on vapor-pressure differences between air and desiccant surfaces. While most materials can hold some moisture, commercial desiccants can absorb from 10% up to 1100% of their weight, depending on type and ambient humidity (Pahlavanzadeh, 2006).

3–16–2–4 Desiccant Operation

A desiccant absorbs moisture until equilibrium. To restore capacity, it is exposed to hot air at about 50–260 °C, depending on moisture content and desiccant type; after releasing water and drying, it is ready for reuse (ibid.).

3–16–2–5 Types of Desiccants

Desiccants are solid or liquid, each with distinct properties. Liquid desiccants generally require lower regeneration temperatures, offer greater design flexibility, and cause less air pressure drop; solid desiccants are compact and less corrosive.

Common desiccants include:

Solids: activated alumina, silica gel, zeolites (molecular sieves), aluminum oxide.
Liquids: lithium chloride solution, sodium bromide solution, ethylene glycol, lithium bromide solution.

Solid desiccants are often applied as a slowly rotating wheel coated with desiccant; one sector absorbs moisture from incoming air while another is regenerated by hot air, enabling continuous operation. Liquid desiccants contact air directly within spray or packed towers (Pahlavanzadeh, 2006).

3–16–2–6 Regeneration Heat Source

A heat source is required to drive off absorbed moisture. Solar energy, waste heat, combustion heat, natural gas, and geothermal energy can be used, enabling energy recovery (Pahlavanzadeh, 2006).

3–16–3 Gas-Based Dehumidification Systems

A gas-cooled radiator can be used to condense moisture from humid air: exposing humid air to a cold, gas-charged radiator lowers air temperature locally so that vapor condenses on the cold surface. Refrigerants (e.g., halogenated hydrocarbons such as Freon-12) can be cyclically expanded and compressed to provide cooling. When gas pressure drops, its temperature falls; compression raises temperature until heat is rejected to surroundings, after which the refrigerant can absorb heat again. Such systems can be devised in residential towers to dehumidify supply air for natural ventilation and to recover a portion of domestic water by condensing atmospheric moisture in Kish’s hot–humid climate (author).

3–17 Potentials of Sustainable Energies Along the Coast

3–17–1 History of Wind-Energy Use in Iran

Iran was the first country to use wind energy for agricultural purposes, with a history of roughly 2,500–3,000 years. This knowledge spread from Iran to other Islamic lands, then to Europe, the Americas, and beyond, for applications such as water pumping and irrigation, grain milling, sawing timber, and crafts.

A well-known ancient Iranian example is the neshtefān windmills of Khāf, renowned worldwide. These vertical-axis mills—reportedly dating to around the seventh century CE in Sistan and the historic district of Neshtefān, Khāf—had six to twelve sails covered with fabric or palm leaves, used for milling grain and lifting water.

3–18 Wind Energy on the Coast

Fossil-fuel scarcity, higher prices, and environmental pollution have driven leading energy users toward renewable, clean sources—especially solar, geothermal, and wind. Use of these sources, particularly in Europe and North America, has grown markedly. Germany now obtains about 21% of its energy from wind farms and plans to produce roughly 10,000 MW of wind power annually by 2020—about 20% of national demand—primarily from offshore and coastal farms, where winds are stronger and more persistent than on land.

3–18–1 Wind Direction on the Coast

Solar heating warms the earth's surface; adjacent air warms, becomes lighter, and rises, while cooler, denser air flows in to replace it—wind. Because solar heating is uneven, polar regions receive less heat than equatorial zones; land also warms and cools faster than water. These differences drive a global heat-exchange system from ground to atmosphere. Much wind energy resides at higher altitudes, where sustained speeds can exceed 160 km/h, eventually dissipating through friction with the earth's surface and the atmosphere.

3–18–2 Wind Speed on the Shores of Kish

Kish Island lies off southern Iran in the Persian Gulf near Hormozgan Province. Based on three-hourly wind data at the Kish station, the annual mean wind speed is 6.8 knots (3.4 m/s). The maximum recorded speed is 74 knots (32.5 m/s) (Kish Free Zone Organization, 2011). Winds above 8 knots are predominantly westerly, and wind direction is stable through much of the year. Given the high speeds, directional stability, and shallow coastal waters, offshore wind farms around Kish could supply the island's electricity much of the year, contributing to environmental protection of Kish and the Gulf and to regional sustainable development (Gandomkar, 2011).

3–18–3 Monthly Mean Wind Speeds on Kish

The Kish station, at 30 m above sea level in the Persian Gulf (Hormozgan Province), reports long-term monthly means indicating that February through June exceed 8 knots on average; in other months, means are around or above 6 knots. Winter and spring are the windiest seasons; late summer and early autumn have the lowest speeds. Thus, February–June are optimal for wind-power generation, while in other months certain hours of the day also exceed 8 knots (Kish Free Zone Organization, 2011).

3–18–4 Kish's National Wind Ranking

Kish ranks fifth nationally after Manjil, Zabol, Rafsanjan, and Khor-Birjand. The maximum recorded speed is 74 knots (32.5 m/s). Wind speeds are 8–16 knots 40.2% of the time, 16–24 knots 31% of the time, and above 42 knots 1% of the time (Gandomkar, 2011).

3–18–5 Principal Wind Directions on Kish

The fastest winds on Kish have a primary westerly and a secondary easterly direction. Because direction is stable in about 74% of cases, wind power generation for residential towers is feasible (Gandomkar, 2011).

3–19 Summary

Wind energy is a renewable resource whose use for electricity is growing rapidly. In Iran it has begun notably in Manjil, but less so elsewhere. Since many countries derive most wind power from offshore and coastal farms—where shallow waters offer optimal conditions—this approach merits attention for protecting Iran’s marine environment. On Kish Island, portions of each day (from noon to night) throughout the year are suitable for wind-power generation; the best period is November through June, when speeds are higher and directions more stable, predominantly westerly. Given high temperatures during this period, wind energy should be prioritized and can significantly support electricity production and ventilation for residential zones on the island.

4: Chapter Four: Case Studies

4-1 Domestic Case Studies

Figure 4-1

4-1-1 Atisaz Residential Complex (Fig. 4-1)

- First to twenty-first floors (residential)
- Ground floor (residential lobby)
- First basement (parking + storage)
- Second basement (parking + storage)
- Roof (mechanical/services)

4-1-1-1 Architectural Quality and Overall Building Aspect

The façade of this complex—despite its novelty and inventiveness, which in itself evokes delight and joy in the viewer—retains a distinct simplicity. One success of the design lies in the clear, straightforward connections for the parking and entrances.

The estate's main street links to the complex at two points:

1. at the dedicated ramp connecting to the underground parking;
2. at the internal circulation network, a loop that encircles Blocks A and B.
3. At present, parking connects to the ground floor via stairs, and direct elevator access from parking to the residential floors has been prevented. According to information received, the initial design provided a dedicated parking elevator to the ground floor in such a way that direct access from parking to residential units without passing the guard was not possible; unfortunately, in execution, stairs alone were built.

4. The ground-floor lobby is expressed by a broad flight of steps down to grade. These portals—bridges from the foot of the steps to the entrance doors over the vehicular network of the basement level—create an inventive and elegant appearance. The setbacks of residential units from floors 1 to 9 in Tower A and from floors 13 to 19 in Tower B are among the noteworthy features that enhance the complex's beauty.

4-1-1-2 Siting, Intervisibility, and Overshadowing Between the Towers

The linear alignment of the blocks and the absence of directly facing windows effectively resolve issues of overlooking and overshadowing. Blocks A and B are spatially connected via the two parking levels. The second basement links by a stair to the grounds and then to Block C.

Daylighting of the towers and distribution of light and space within the residential units: Blocks A and B, with linear plans, receive light from two directions, while Block C, with a centralized, square plan, receives light from four sides. The blocks are set at a 25-degree angle west of the north-south axis.

Most units in Blocks A and B are single-aspect; in Block B - all units are dual-aspect.

4-1-1-3 Assessment of Nuisance Noise

The location of the selected blocks—and indeed of the Atisaz estate as a whole—places them at a remove from nuisance noise.

4-1-1-4 Tower Entrances and Daylighting of Main Stairs and Corridors

Compared to other complexes, this project gives notable prominence to block entrances; the entry points read as major nodes.

Each block has one principal entrance from the grounds and one entrance from the underground parking. The stair and elevator cores are placed to allow direct access to daylight and natural ventilation; on floors with gallery-type corridors flanked by units on both sides, the corridors themselves do not receive direct light and air. Noteworthy is the integration of the emergency stair with the main stair—in other words, the absence of a separate emergency stair—which is among the reasons for reduced common areas.

Residential unit entries along gallery corridors are positioned so they do not directly face one another, avoiding mutual disturbance. The number of elevators in Towers A and B is two

(1.5 × 2 m and 2 × 2 m), and in Tower C two (2.5 × 2.5 m). In this complex, one elevator is provided per 22 dwelling units.

4-1-1-5 Inter-Views Between the Towers, Views to the City, and Fit with the Context

Because key considerations have been observed, inter-views between towers do not cause nuisance. The favorable urban position affords desirable city vistas. The Atisaz estate, in its parceling, building heights, and architectural character, is distinct within the area and shares little with neighboring fabric.

4-1-1-6 Plant Room Location, Equipment, and Maintenance System

The main plant serving Towers A, B, and C is outside these towers, in the Phase One estate plant, which serves nine towers. Heating of basement areas is provided by subsidiary plant rooms. Fan-coils and chillers supply heating and cooling. Heating for nonresidential areas—except the educational center—is provided by private plant rooms. A 100 m³ storage tank is located in the plant and is operated by nine booster pumps. Floors 1–9, 10–15, and 15–21 are each served by separate pumps. There are 4 boilers and 6 chillers; the fuel is gasoil, with 6 fuel tanks (Alami, 2000)

Residential density: 589%	Percentage of area under road network: 34%
Building density: 589%	Number of towers: 3
District 2	Site coverage ratio: 27%
Site area: 112,250	Number of floors: 27%
Sides adjoining streets: 4	Number of basement levels: 2
Shortest distance to main street: 100	Common areas per dwelling unit: 53
Frontage per dwelling unit: 14.5	Total number of units: 198
Common areas per dwelling unit: 53	Frontage per dwelling unit: 14.5
Density: 589%	Land per dwelling unit: 56.8
Open space per dwelling unit: 7.2	Total number of units: 198
Number of residential floors: 21 and 2/1	

4–2 International Case Studies

Figure 4-2

4–2–2 Bahrain World Trade Center (BWTC) (Fig. 4-2)

The Bahrain World Trade Center (also known as Bahrain WTC or BWTC) is a 240-metre twin-tower complex constructed in Manama, Bahrain. Three wind turbines are mounted between the towers to supply a portion of the complex’s electricity. Each skyscraper has 50 floors, and the pair currently ranks as the second-tallest buildings in Bahrain. The towers were built between 2004 and 2008 at a reported cost of USD 150 million.

The siting, scale, and aerodynamic design are reinforced by the system of sky-bridges between the towers. The three unique 29-metre turbines installed between them channel the prevailing Gulf Sea breeze through the turbine corridors—chimney-like—to enhance generator efficiency. Prior to construction, numerous concerns were raised regarding turbine noise for occupants; the loads transmitted to the two towers via the bridge structures; and the effects of lightning and bird movement on turbine operation. All such scenarios were analyzed with their associated hazards and risks. The turbines are equipped with optical sensors that, upon detecting the approach of an object such as a bird or the presence of lightning, automatically command shutdown. Turbine noise is largely mitigated by internal acoustic-control systems. The turbines were first commissioned in April 2008 to test performance and confirm the resolution of identified issues.

Each turbine generates 225 kW, yielding a total capacity of 675 kW; calculations indicate that the turbines provide approximately 10–15% of the building’s energy demand. Although the precise service life is uncertain, the builders state that, given the unobstructed site and the “clean” wind passing the turbines, their life may extend to 20 years.

4-3 Examples of Towers Adapted to Local Wind Flows

4-3-1 Jean-Marie Tjibaou Cultural Center (Fig. 4-3)

Figure 40-3

Italian architect Renzo Piano, in the Jean-Marie Tjibaou Cultural Center in New Caledonia, created a synthesis of tradition and technology in such a way that the center helped the island's people—especially the Kanaks—face the future while preserving their culture, turning the complex into a symbol for construction in the new millennium. In this design, the slope of the ground together with architectural and vegetative windbreaks is used to control airflow, so that the building is in complete accord with its setting and with local wind patterns. The climatic question—pursued in parallel with research on vernacular buildings and advanced testing on models at various scales, particularly wind-tunnel trials—provided the basis for using wind to regulate the temperature of the outer double-skin wall and to achieve natural ventilation of the interior.

Few designs have addressed architecture and sustainable development simultaneously so effectively. Ventilation is achieved by admitting cool air currents at the upper portion of the structure. The “cases” are configured to receive winds that blow almost constantly from a single direction and to lower the internal temperature continuously by exhausting warm air. These structures are, of course, engineered to withstand all climatic events, especially tropical

cyclones. The smaller buildings establish a close relationship with the surrounding natural environment. Valuing the landscape in New Caledonia is an art deeply tied to Kanak culture. Piano consistently seeks entirely original solutions, drawing on diverse technologies and materials to answer the project's premises. For him the aim is light, not a particular kind of window; lightness, not a particular kind of structure. He unites the inventor, the artist, and the craftsman, and avoids any prepackaged solution. His sensitivity to space, place, and the profound meaning of use recalls Louis Kahn, in whose office Piano worked for a time in 1969 (Rah Shahr International Group, 2011).

4-3-2 Commerzbank, Germany (Fig.4-4)

Figure 4-4

This building was designed by the renowned British firm Foster + Partners (Norman Foster). To establish direct contact with nature and enable natural ventilation, the scheme employs open floors configured as sky gardens together with a central courtyard (atrium). Airflow penetrates all levels of the tower, providing natural ventilation throughout. The building features a very tall atrium and four-story garden vistas distributed over the full height of the structure (source: Rah Shahr International Group, 2011).

Its ventilation structure is organized around a central core. These architectural elements open up the Commerzbank's interior and fundamentally transform the environment. Notable characteristics include:

1. Using limited environmental energy to reduce dependence on fossil fuels through an innovative façade and natural-ventilation system.
2. Providing health and well-being for users by means of operable windows and sky gardens.
3. Recycling greywater for building cooling and sanitary uses.

Commerzbank, completed in 1997, was the tallest building of its time; more importantly, it drew attention for the distinctive qualities of its construction (source: Rah Shahr International Group, 2011).

4–5 Summary

By understanding the rules governing wind and its architectural traces, wind flows can be harnessed in three domains: natural building ventilation, environmental and building cooling, and the control of undesirable winds. To this end, one must first identify how wind behaves when encountering and passing around obstacles, and then examine the influence of wind flows on the formation of each region's architecture—including the density, form, and orientation of urban fabric and buildings, as well as the characteristics of open, semi-open, and edge spaces. This approach is among the principal reasons for the emergence of climate-responsive architecture.

5: Chapter Five: Design Process

Study Area

5-1 Kish Island

Kish Island is one of the islands of the Persian Gulf and is administratively part of Kish District, Bandar Lengeh County, Hormozgan Province, in southern Iran. In the past it was known as “Fīsh.” The island is oval in shape and lies about 12 km off the Shibkuh coast.

5-2 Economic Capacities of Kish

Kish possesses distinctive natural assets. Calm beaches with coral sands and exceptionally clear seawater—allowing observation of marine life at a depth of several meters—together with a suitable vegetative cover and pervasive greenery, especially over seven months of the year, create striking and scenic vistas that attract roughly one million nature and sea enthusiasts annually.

5-3 Geographical Location of Kish Island

Kish Island covers 91 km², has a shoreline of 43 km, and is approximately oval. It lies 18 km from Band-e Garzeh (Bandar-e Aftab) on the Iranian mainland, within the Persian Gulf. Situated in the first quarter of Iran’s 1,359-km southern coastline, at the mouth of the Persian Gulf and near the terminal section of this waterway within the Strait of Hormuz, its latitude is 26°32′ N and its longitude 53°58′ E. The island extends 15.45 km from the western to the eastern shore (from the Marjan Complex to Hoor Square). Its maximum north–south width (from the Customs Port to the Lighthouse) is 7.5 km. The island’s surface lacks pronounced topography such as mountains or even high hills. Kish International Airport is located near the center on a relatively elevated area at approximately 35 m above sea level. The island’s greatest slope runs from north of the airport toward the coast (Fig. 5-0).

Figure 05-0

5-4 Geology of the Island

In terms of coastal morphology, the visible form of Kish Island can be divided into two principal types:

1. rocky and cliffed shores;
2. sandy shores.
3. The emergence of these two types is chiefly a function of prevailing wave directions. The island's ground is predominantly coral limestone, which constitutes the main component of its raw materials and soils. Surveys across the island show that the principal lithologic layer overlying the island's clayey sediments—and effectively covering most of the surface—is a coquina, a cemented calcareous mix of gravels, shells, and shell fragments. The thickness of this layer reaches about 20 m, diminishing to 3–4 m near the coast. After the island formed, periodic changes in the Persian Gulf's Sea level—and episodes of relative rise, sometimes prolonged—submerged the island in shallow water. The relative warmth, shallow depth, abundant light, and other favorable environmental conditions created an optimal setting for the growth of corals, marine organisms, reefs, and shells on the submerged surface. Over time, a compact stratum of their calcareous remains formed coral-limestone rock on the inundated surface of the island. Kish is considered the world's largest coral island. Coral islands and tropical forests exhibit the highest biodiversity among global ecosystems; these sensitive marine organisms—especially in the tropics—play a vital role in the stability and continuity of oceanic life. Coral reefs also underpin the resilience and permanence of local communities. For this reason, conserving this valuable asset is of great environmental importance for the Persian Gulf region.

5-5 Island Slope

Overall, ground slopes on Kish Island are less than ten percent. Approximately half of the island's surface has slopes under one percent. Contour mapping shows a general westward fall, meaning the eastern half is higher than the western half and, relative to other parts of the island, somewhat steeper. Nonetheless, slope-related irregularities do not pose difficulties for physical construction. (Kish Free Zone Organization, 2011)

5-6 Mean Temperature

Latitude and elevation strongly condition temperature, the principal climatic element. Kish lies at a low latitude; its mean daily summer temperature ranges from 32.3 to 33.6 °C, with relative humidity between 66% and 69%. Relative to Iran’s summer comfort zone (approximately 21.5–29 °C and 30–65% RH), summer conditions are unfavorable. In winter the mean daily temperature ranges from 18.2 to 20.4 °C, with relative humidity between 65% and 71%, which—relative to Iran’s winter comfort zone (approximately 20–26 °C and 60–75% RH)—yields moderate and favorable conditions. (Kish Free Zone Organization, 2011)

5-7 Humidity

Water-vapor pressure on the island is very high during most of the year (relative humidity commonly 50–60%). The annual diurnal temperature range is under 9–10 °C, and temperatures never fall to freezing. Meteorological data indicate that the average specific humidity of Kish’s warm, dry air is about 15 g/kg in January and about 25 g/kg in July. From October to April the weather is mild and pleasant, and environmental conditions are favorable. From May to September the island is hot and sultry; in May, as the sea is still cool and relative humidity is lower, the air is comparatively dry and the wind gentle and breeze-like—overall springlike and agreeable. The difference between the warmest and coldest months is roughly 16 °C: January records the lowest evaporation, with about 12% variability, and is the coolest and driest month; August shows the highest evaporation, with roughly 28% variability, and is the hottest month. High summer evaporation also relates to the occasional convective showers that occur as monsoonal moisture from the Indian Ocean reaches the area. (Kish Free Zone Organization, 2011)

Month	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec
Average	68.5	72	74	86	66	69	71	71.5	72	66	60	65.5

(Source: Kish Free Zone Organization)

5-8 Sunshine Hours

According to the pyranometer records at the Kish station, the mean total annual sunshine duration on the island is about 3,183.4 hours. The highest and lowest monthly sunshine hours—335 and 131 hours—occur in June and February, respectively. Given this, harnessing the island’s abundant solar resource for electricity generation, dynamic applications, and space and site heating can serve as a principal energy supply in buildings. (Ibid.)

5–9 Island Winds

According to data from the Meteorological Organization, the prevailing wind blows from the west throughout the year. The least frequent winds are the gentle breezes from the north and south. Summer southerlies increase slightly in frequency due to heating over the Arabian Peninsula, while northerlies remain negligible year-round. In the five coldest months, easterlies are the next most frequent after the prevailing westerlies. (Fig 5.0)

Maximum recorded wind speed on Kish is 72 km/h in February (from the west). All high-speed winds are westerly; only in September and October do relatively strong winds blow from the east and northeast. Under the hot–humid conditions of the Persian Gulf, using wind energy for ventilation and as a sustainable building power source is highly effective. (Kish Free Zone Organization, 2011)

The Gulf’s shallow coastal waters and island shores are well suited to wind-turbine installation. In areas with persistent winds above 8 knots (4 m/s), wind turbines can be used for various purposes, including agricultural water pumping and electricity generation.

5–10 Wave Energy and the Coast of Kish

The Persian Gulf does not exhibit uniform characteristics across its extent; parameters such as salinity, clarity, wave height, and tides vary.

Tides: Generally, the Gulf experiences two tidal cycles every 24 hours. Along the Kish shoreline, maximum and minimum water levels reach about 1.9 m and 1.5 m, respectively. Waves: The maximum recorded wave height in the Persian Gulf is about 10 m, whereas off Kish the height does not exceed 3 m. Accordingly, in considering renewable energy, wave energy can be utilized on Kish to help meet residents’ needs; marine waves constitute an important energy resource for the island. (Lari, 2005)

5–11 Reasons for Site Selection

Kish Island is one of Iran’s key islands in the Persian Gulf, with significant economic and natural energy potential. Designing a residential tower with a sustainable approach can both support economic infrastructure and employ renewable energies in the region. A residential tower on Kish that leverages renewables could become a regional symbol—both in scale and form and in the application of advanced design technologies. For this reason, the proposed site—approximately 12,000 m²—has been selected on Kish Island near the pier, on the

shoreline, to maximize access to environmental energies and to present visitors with a novel architectural-technology landmark.

5-12 Project Specifications

5-12-1 Project Study Area

Spatial-locational context of the project with site plans:

The site lies on the Kish shoreline, directly on the Persian Gulf, and is designated for residential use. The parcel area for design is 12,000 m². (Fig. 5-1)

Figure 50-1

The proposed project provides approximately 5,000 m² of residential gross floor area, accounting for the coastal setback, with 40% site coverage and 12 stories on the selected site, together with full recreational and service amenities for residents' comfort. The design adopts a generative design/sustainable development approach.

Aerial photographs of the site location

13-5 Physical Program

5-13-1 Space Categories

Public spaces:

- Entrance
- Living room (Reception)
- Dining room

Private spaces:

- Family room (Lounge)
- Bedrooms
- Wet spaces:
 - Bathroom
 - Toilet
 - Kitchen
- Support spaces:
 - Parking
 - Mechanical/Electrical services
- Amenity spaces:
 - Gym
 - Retail
 - Swimming pool
- **Space name: Entrance**
 - Time of use: Throughout the day
 - Use: Circulation in and out
 - Adjacencies: Hall, kitchen, toilet, living room (reception)
 - Ventilation: Preferably natural
 - Note: Visibility from the kitchen over arrivals/departures should be possible.
- **Space name: Kitchen**
 - Time of use: Daytime
 - Use: Preparation, washing, cooking
 - Ventilation: Preferably mechanical; continuous fan to prevent ceiling condensation
 - Requirement: The kitchen work triangle should not exceed 6.6 m in total.
- **Space name: Dining room**
 - Time of use: Day and night
 - Use: Family or guest dining
 - Adjacencies: Kitchen and living room (reception)
 - Ventilation: Natural

- **Furnishings: Table and chairs**

- Dining table for 1–2 persons: 75 × 75 cm

- Dining table for 6 persons: 100 × 120 cm

- Round table for 6 persons: Ø120 cm

- Dining table for 8 persons: 180 × 100 cm

- Dining table for 12 persons: 240 × 100 cm

- Dining chair: 45 × 45 cm

- Allow 80 cm per chair for seating plus access

- **Space name: Bedroom**

- Time of use: Day (children: play/study) and night (sleep)

- Use: Rest and comfort while occupied

- Adjacencies: Private Hall, bathroom

- Ventilation: Natural

- Note: Layout should allow flexible furniture arrangements.

- **Space name: Living room (Reception)**

- Time of use: Day and night

- Use: Hosting guests and gatherings

- Adjacencies: Private Hall, kitchen, entrance

- Ventilation: Natural

- **Space name: Family room (Lounge)**

- Time of use: Day and night

- Use: Daily family gatherings

- Adjacencies: Bedrooms, kitchen, dining room

- Ventilation: Natural

- **Space name: Bathroom/Toilet**

- Use: Hygiene and bathing

- Adjacencies: Bedrooms, family room

- Ventilation: Natural and mechanical

- **Space name: Parking**

Use: Covered parking for residents' vehicles, adjacent to each unit or block

Adjacencies: Entrance

Ventilation: Natural and mechanical

Dimensions: 3 × 5 m per stall

Table 1-5 Overall Summary of Spaces

Space	Household size (3 persons) m ²	Household size (4 persons) m ²	Household size (5 persons) m ²
55 Residential Units	1680	2500	3000
Parking (including accessible parking)	315	315	320
Circulation & Structure Allowance (30% of residential + parking)	598	844	996
MEP Allowance (10% of residential)	168	250	300
Total	2761	3909	4616

Total floor area of all residential units in the Kish residential tower: 11,286 m²

2-5 Idea and Concept

The historical trend of the courtyard's retreat from residential space in favor of the street and the city—and the decision to restore this layer to the dwelling—constitutes the initial idea of this project. (Fig. 5-2)

Figure 50-2

Giving equal value to the courtyard as Void and the Mass as the enclosed, roofed space.
 Also, creating a porous fabric of Mass and Void and providing space for wind to pass through.
 (Fig. 5-3)

Figure 0-3

Figure5-4

Figure5-5

- Study on the integration of courtyard typologies within a tower. (Fig. 5-4)
- Study on the combination of courtyard typologies. (Fig. 5-5)

Impact of the selected features on the initial gene. (Figure 5-6)

Figure 0-6

Figure 5-7

Sub-Type Generation (Figure 5-7)

Generative Design in a Semi-Automated Process

Each type should include three main features as part of its genetic design:

1. **Wind:** Inspired by the typologies of southern coastal cities in Iran, wind flow is utilized to improve environmental comfort and create a pleasant microclimate.
2. **Double-Height Balcony:** The traditional courtyard is reinterpreted as double-height balconies, establishing a spatial quality that blends the openness of a courtyard with the functionality of a balcony.
3. **View:** Every unit must have at least one façade oriented toward the coast, ensuring both the best scenic perspective and access to abundant natural light. (Fig. 5-8)

Selection of a linear placement on the site due to the importance of views on the eastern side of the site (sea view), and adoption of this characteristic as one of the influential features in the gene. (Fig. 5-8)

Figure 5-8

Figure 05-9

Vertical Circulation Diagram (Fig. 5-9)

3–5 Conclusion

Optimal utilization of environmental conditions is among the principles of sustainable architecture. Accordingly, when making the initial design decisions, the siting of the building plays a fundamental role and is among the first priorities. To make optimal use of positive environmental factors, including available natural energies, an appropriate understanding of the environment, the climatic conditions, and their positive and negative capacities is required.

With sufficient knowledge and correct responses to environmental conditions, achieving climatic compatibility and reducing energy consumption becomes easier, and providing the requisites of comfort for residents becomes less costly.

In residential architecture, providing cost-effective comfort conditions for daily life within the architectural environment is a basic principle. Accordingly, considering the building as part of a whole—part of nature and part of the climatic conditions—has been one of the fundamental objectives and considerations for the architect of this residential complex. From this perspective, the architect has examined the site, form, materials, and structure with the aim of reducing energy consumption while maintaining occupant comfort.

Daylight is of great importance to the designer, and the use of solar energy is highly valuable. The building should be designed to provide sufficient light whenever the sun is above the horizon. Naturally, glare and excessive heat must be avoided. Therefore, in a successful strategy, façade design and ventilation are key elements.

In the course of architectural design, one can study existing natural models in the region—their adaptation to the environment, their placement in nature, their encounter with climatic conditions, and their use of the environment and natural strategies that have evolved over hundreds of years and selected the best course—and apply them. In this project, an effort has been made to return the layers removed from residential space back into the dwelling.

Conceiving residential environments that do not conflict with the principles and methods of sustainability, nor with occupant comfort, must be addressed so that the designed residential spaces, in addition to employing principles of sustainability, can provide an appropriate living environment.

The design of these spaces can be shaped by studying the non-technological engagement with nature by predecessors and by employing technology alongside it and the relationships between them, so that principles of sustainability can be integrated more simply.

An important point in designing a sustainable residential tower is the correct combination and creative use of technologies, and efforts have been made to ensure that the proposed solutions are not inappropriately inserted into the building’s physical form.

Among the strategies used in the design of the Kish residential tower is the appropriate placement of the building on the project site to enable full utilization of wind energy. The principal orientation of the building is toward the west—the strongest direction of the prevailing wind—and the porosity created in the structure provides effective natural ventilation.

In this study, an attempt was made to examine the factors necessary to create a sustainable tower. Architecture engages with energy in two ways:

- 1 – Passive
- 2 – Active

By Active is meant the use of technology to produce energy or to save energy after construction; for example, solar energy, which was discussed in Chapter Two.

By Passive is meant architectural design intended to reduce or optimize space, which contributes to energy saving and sustainability.

In the design of this tower, the priority is Passive design, and the author believes that sustainability can be enhanced through the Active approach.

Site plan (Fig. 5-10):

Figure 5-10

3-5 Drawings

Perspective and type diagrams: (Fig. 5-11)

Figure 5-0-11

Combination and optimization: (Fig. 5-12)

Figure 0-12

Plan and section type 1 and 2: (Fig. 5-13)

Figure 0-13

Plan and section type 3 and 4: (Fig. 5-14)

Figure5-14

Elevations and Sections: (Fig. 5-15)

Figure5-15

Courtyard's perspective and Site plan: (Fig. 5-16)

Figure5-16

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